

Pop-Machina

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Market research report

Deliverable 2.2

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Abstract

The report presents the main findings of the large-scale survey that has been conducted during the Pop-Machina project aiming to capture the insights about makerspaces' acceptance, main drivers and barriers. The large-scale survey included all EU countries and the analysis of the results will focus on capturing the main outcomes regarding general EU citizens' perceptions and potential differences between EU Member states. The report is structured as follows. Section 3 presents a literature review regarding the main drivers, barriers and challenges of makerspaces, in order to present the current state-of-the-art in the field of collaborative production. Section 4 includes all information related to the survey design and the implementation. In Section 5, we present some initial descriptive findings closely related to individual perceptions and levels of acceptance and highlight any significant variations between different EU areas. Section 5 also includes the main statistical analysis of the dataset by including the outcomes of the factor analysis and logit model that we have built. KPIs related to this deliverable are presented in Section 6, whereas conclusions and further discussion are given in Section 7.

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1. Introduction

Exploring the current state-of-the-art of the collaborative production and makerspaces across Europe is essential for providing and developing an effective policy framework towards empowering the uptake of makerspaces and fablabs. Lack of awareness and low social acceptance levels can greatly affect the course of these projects and can emerge as significant barriers for clean-energy transition. Especially in the case of collaborative production projects that require a complex multi-actor involvement, social acceptance can pose a serious threat to the successful implementation and sustainability of the project.

With the aim to gain insights into the main drivers boosting social acceptance of makerspaces and collaborative production projects, and in order to identify possible barriers and gaps limiting a wider adoption of these initiatives, a large-scale European survey was conducted as part of the Pop-Machina project. The focus was on capturing awareness levels regarding makerspaces and their position on global value chains, social acceptance factors that affect its implementation and any potential differences in perceptions between countries, stakeholder groups, and types of regions. The key findings of the survey will inform the National and EU Strategic plans to take effective policy measures for the promotion of collaborative production projects throughout Europe.

2. Main scope

Urban growth and prosperity have led world's population to consume 1.6 times more than its global capacity, with no signs of decline.¹ Existing linear consumption models lead to enormous waste² with impacts on health, food, resource reuse, and environmental sustainability. Europe has been investing in a circular plan for production, consumption, processing, storage, recycling and disposal (EC, 2014) and despite the significant progress, cities still struggle to implement a full circular economy model due to a variety of barriers (cultural, technical, market and regulatory). Cities must cope with these challenges under increasingly regressing conditions: fragmentation of the value ecosystem, reduced budgets and social issues (e.g. inequality and marginalisation) and their consequent spatial effects such as urban sprawl, urban decay and overurbanisation (Panori et al., 2019a, b; Angelidou et al., 2018).

Meanwhile, an underlying trend has been gaining attention and traction: collaborative production and the makers movement. The prosumer trend, the rapid expansion of open workshops (makerspaces),³ the increase of availability and affordability of digital fabrication tools such as 3D printers and laser cutters and the advance in certain collaborative technologies have led to the creation of a rapidly increasing number of Do-It-Yourself communities (DIY). These communities typically develop and market products that are recreated and assembled using urban mining of secondary raw materials (like unused, discarded or broken electronic metals, plastic, silicon from technological hardware). All around the world,⁴ the maker movement is being heralded as a driver for the new 'industrial revolution1' and for good reasons.

Collaborative production, however, like most nascent fields, still has many challenges to overcome before it can reach its potential. The EC acknowledges that common collaborative production challenges include scaling up of manufacturing to a sufficiently large scale, lack of viable business models and the tension between democratised manufacturing and existing market regulations (EC, 2015). The latter is also connected to issues of safety and quality of community manufactured goods. On top of these rather macro-level barriers, some subtler interconnected issues exist; maker communities still struggle between the sharing approach and the entrepreneurial one, causing resistance to scaling efforts; in some cases, perceptions about makerspaces can limit local support.⁵ The makers' community is calling for increased networking and network experience, sharing and adoption of best practices and a more holistic, culturally expansive, and community-centric role for makerspaces.⁶ The EC is urging policy makers to support collaborative production by encouraging shared physical manufacturing infrastructure and networks and calls for regulation that encourages and mainstreams democratised manufacturing (EC, 2015). Researchers argue that to be able to tackle these barriers and inform effective policy and application, planners need to understand the stakeholders (Kominos et al., 2019; Wolf-Powers et al., 2017; Angelidou & Psaltoglou, 2017) and align with the benefits of scaling production (Unterfrauner et al., 2017).

The report presents the main findings of the large-scale survey that has been conducted during the Pop-Machina project aiming to capture the insights about makerspaces' acceptance, main drivers,

1 <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2015/aug/12/humans-have-already-used-up-2015s-supply-of-earths-resources-analysis>

2 ELLEN MACARTHUR

https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/assets/downloads/publications/EllenMacArthurFoundation_PolicymakerToolkit.pdf

3 We use 'makerspaces' throughout this proposal as a term that includes fab labs, hackerspaces and repair cafes.

4 <http://europeanmakerweek.eu/>

5 <https://hackernoon.com/in-france-cyber-criticism-turns-violent-as-activists-burn-a-fablab-to-protest-the-diffusion-of-4ad378251c5b>

6 American Society for Engineering Education. Envisioning the Future of the maker movement: Summit Report. 2016.

and barriers. The large-scale survey included all EU countries and the analysis of the results will focus on capturing the main outcomes regarding general EU citizens' perceptions and potential differences between EU Member states. The report is structured as follows. Section 3 presents a literature review regarding the main drivers, barriers and challenges of makerspaces, in order to present the current state-of-the-art in the field of collaborative production. Section 4 includes all information related to the survey design and the implementation. In Section 5, we present some initial descriptive findings closely related to individual perceptions and levels of acceptance and highlight any significant variations between different EU areas. Section 5 also includes the main statistical analysis of the dataset by including the outcomes of the factor analysis and logit model that we have built. KPIS related to this deliverable are presented in Section 6, whereas conclusions and further discussion are given in Section 7.

3. Literature review

It is common knowledge that the world is changing. In this context, population experiences a continuous increase, alongside lifestyles and trends that are constantly changing. Greater levels of consumption are observed, followed by enormous quantities of waste. In this context and in accordance with the principles of Sustainable Development, a strategy for a transition towards a circular economy has been developed. In Europe, a circular plan for production, consumption, processing, and disposal sets the framework within which cities implement a circular economy model driving towards sustainable growth. Meanwhile, an underlying trend has been gaining momentum: the collaborative production and the maker movement. Over the last decade, the maker economy has been attracting attention while an immense growth of communities engaged in Do-It-Yourself (DIY) activities has been observed (Rosa et al., 2018; 2017). On this basis, much research on the maker movement has been done, shedding light on its culture, approaches, and perspectives.

3.1 What is the maker movement?

Although the term ‘maker movement’ is still a subject of discussion, several publications (Rosa et al., 2018, 2017; Bean et al., 2015; Wittemyer et al., 2014) describe it as a branch of the more general DIY movement, that combines cutting-edge technologies with more traditional arts and crafts activities, and promotes learning, innovation, design thinking and hands-on approaches.

The physical representation of the maker movement includes spaces such as Makerspaces, FabLabs and Hackerspaces. The aim of these initiatives is to provide makers and their communities the infrastructures and technical equipment that can enable them to turn their ideas into reality. While the diffusion of such spaces is impressive (Bean et al., 2015), it is far from being geographically homogeneous. Data collected from previous EU studies (Rosa et al., 2018) indicate that Western European countries have a higher number of Makerspaces. This could imply that there is a connection between the level of a community’s economic development and the uptake of the maker movement. Nevertheless, makerspaces are present in all major EU cities, indicating a significant spatial allocation of the makers movement to all EU countries. In fact, it appears that makerspaces flourish in large urban environments since the latter offer significant benefits such as access to customers, early adopters, more socially conscious and environmentally aware citizens, etc. (Schrock et al., 2016).

3.2 Who are the makers?

Apart from the physical spaces, another key element of the maker movement is the people who participate; the makers. Literature defines makers as people who create a range of products from crafts to home improvements to self-service with information technology (Collier & Wayment, 2018; Kwon & Lee, 2017). Regardless the terminology, makers are people who share a passion about their hobbies, handcrafts, grass-root innovations, and DIY projects.

The current knowledge about makers comes mostly from qualitative studies. According to these studies, makers range from hobbyists to traditional artisans to more advanced software developers, and could include craftsmen, designers, artists, musicians, cooks, students, welders, scientists, engineers, software developers (Kwon & Lee, 2017; Wittemyer, 2014). In this sense, ‘we are all makers’

as Dougherty, the founder of MAKE company states, meaning that everyone engages in making or at least has the potential to do so (Masters, 2018).

3.3 Demographics of the makers

Previous research has observed a variety of demographic characteristics related to the makers (Wittemyer, 2014; Make & Intel, 2012). According to it, approximately 80% of the makers participating in the Makerspaces are males whereas only 20% are women. Moreover, the median age of female participants is 28 years of age, while the median age of adult male makers is 34 years old. Other authors indicate that among makers youth and children play a significant role (Hartmann & Mietzner, 2017). Over eight in ten (83%) are employed and nearly one-third of them have job titles or job descriptions in technical areas. Besides that, makers are clearly a well-educated group, with 97% having attended or graduated from college; 80% having post-graduate education and over four in ten holding post-graduate degrees. Some of the most common degrees amongst makers include engineering, as well as computer and information science. More specifically, male ‘makers’ are mainly engaged in science and engineering, while women ‘makers’ are mainly engaged in arts. Furthermore, participants of makerspaces report a high median household income and most of them are married.

The above information offers some insight regarding the maker’s profile that calls for further inquiry. The low representation of women in the maker movement, the makers’ young age, their educational profile, and others, raise a series of questions that need to be further investigated:

- What are the specific participation challenges for women?
- Do the elderly find it difficult to take part in making activities? Why?
- Are people who do not have tertiary education involved in the maker movement? If not, why?
- Why do unemployed and economically disadvantaged people have lower participation rates?
- What type of training would empower vulnerable groups, such as uneducated, unemployed and people of low economic status, to be involved?
- How important is engineering, IT and technical knowledge and skills for participating in the maker movement?

Current studies analyse and compare various aspects that characterise participants of the maker movement. Nevertheless, very few of them investigate whether specific social groups are underrepresented within makers’ communities (Seo, 2019). In practice, despite the movement’s claims of universality, there is consistent reproduction of exclusion cases (Whelan, 2018). As reported in the literature, most of the members of Makerspaces are ‘technically interested and well educated and, therefore, represent a particular fraction of society’ (Waldman-Brown et al., 2016). Overall, the above indicate that, while inclusiveness of making comes across as one of the key characteristics of the maker movement, whether the movement is inclusive for everyone, remains in question.

3.4 Drivers influencing engagement in making

Even though the maker movement is constantly growing, studies on the motivational factors that affect community participation in the making activities are still lacking (Kwon & Lee, 2017). Nevertheless, current research offers some indications for aspects that can support the uptake of this social phenomenon. For instance, makers’ prior DIY experience in terms of skills, as well as materials knowledge, positively influences their decision to participate in such projects. Moreover, the benefits derived from STEM education in terms of abilities and skills are one of the main factors that make Makerspaces appealing, especially to children and youth. In fact, the relevant literature shows that the maker movement and STEM education are closely related, and makers are interested in how the STEM fields can help them expand their knowledge through making (Sang & Simpson, 2019). Also,

together with an interest in learning, the will to experiment is among the top motivations (Menichinelli et al., 2017). Besides that, it seems that people must have discretionary time to engage in making activities (Wolf & McQuitty, 2011).

Several authors found that motivations also include economic benefits and economic savings (Collier & Wayment, 2017; Wolf & McQuitty, 2011). The lack of available high-quality products together with the need for more customised products that better fit their needs, also motivates people. Furthermore, the growing anti-consumption and more sustainable lifestyle patterns seem to be among the key drivers for the engagement. Along these lines, the use of recycled and reclaimed materials in the produced work and crafts, significantly motivates people (Collier & Wayment, 2017). The existence of available urban locations is also an important factor, since it helps makers to build the knowledge and, especially, the relationships that will further enable them to be involved in making activities (Wolf-Powers, 2016). However, even though having a common co-working space where makers can share tools is important, what also motivates participation is the community spirit and the co-existence of a variety of different mindsets. As such, the opportunity to be in touch with people of different competences and exchange knowledge, experiences and skills seems to be a significant driver towards community participation in the maker movement.

Most makers also indicate as important factors the desire to create, the craftsman identity (i.e. a type of social labelling), the feeling of creating something from start to finish, as well as the enjoyment of socialising and participating in a DIY community. Furthermore, the need for uniqueness and differentiation from other people, as well as the sense of empowerment, open-sharing and learning, creativity, accomplishment, self-improvement, fun and enjoyment that making activities offer, are considered to be core motivational factors (Collier & Wayment, 2017; Wolf & McQuitty, 2011). At the same time, even though the maker movement is not directly associated with sharing and, most of the participants highlighted that they are more essential compared to general information, technical knowledge, the organisation of initiatives, places for work and files and resources (Menichinelli et al., 2017).

Overall, the motivation for participating in maker initiatives is mostly related with personal and generic objectives such as learning about making, using making for education and developing personal projects. Other motivations such as developing collaborative solutions, improving business through making or improving policymaking, appear to be subordinate (MAKE-IT project, 2017).

3.5 Challenges in participating in the maker movement

Makers, however, still have many challenges to overcome before they engage in Makerspaces and making activities. Several authors indicate a variety of barriers that affect people's decision to participate in the maker movement. According to relevant studies, makers can be discouraged by the lack of income stemming from these initiatives, the insufficient available information, the lack of mentorship as well as the limited access to tools and materials (Bean et al., 2015; Wittemyer et al., 2014). Besides that, the fear of failure and criticism together with the fear of the unknown are supposed to be among the top challenges.

Moreover, the lack of technical skills seems to be a barrier since 'creating an object from an idea to the finished thing using a digital drawing and other technology is not a straightforward process'. As such, this process makes it difficult for anyone to walk into a Makerspace and start creating some product immediately (Waldman-Brown et al., 2015). This is in line with another part of the literature which suggests that the competence of people to execute the necessary tasks will significantly affect their motivation and willingness to join. For example, in cases where a person wants to actively join the maker movement, they should be willing as well feeling able to join (MAKE-IT, 2017). Furthermore, some of the potential participants are also concerned about more general contextual aspects, since they perceive makerspaces to be too loud, dusty, and disorganised workspaces. Other potential

barriers are the absence of a clearly defined goals from the making process, as well as the limited awareness of what Makerspaces are and what benefits they can provide (Lewis, 2015).

Apart from these general factors identified in the literature, previous research has documented more specific challenges faced by underrepresented social groups. The maker movement, struggle with rather homogeneous audiences, since it is difficult to attract nearby-living minority groups such as low-income groups, diverse ethnic groups, and minorities, etc. Even though maker initiatives (e.g., Makerspaces, FabLabs) take place mostly at a local or regional scale, they often lack an approach for being more inclusive towards various types of makers (MAKE-IT, 2017). In relation to gender, as documented in the literature, any potentially existing gender gaps might arise mostly due to existing norms related to gender imbalances, stereotypes, and biases (Maric, 2018; Bean et al., 2015; Lewis, 2015; Wittemyer et al., 2014). Overall, it seems that makerspaces are a male-dominated environment in which women face difficulties in finding a role. Consequently, Makerspaces appear to be an environment where female makers participation, requires a higher amount of engagement effort. Furthermore, researchers observe that women underrepresentation within the maker movement is also related with their tendency to drift away from STEM fields and related careers. As such, the overriding feeling and/or misconception is that women are less interested in technical activities which are closely related with STEM (Bean et al., 2015). Further to the above obstacles, female makers also struggle to find free time to join makerspaces due to family obligations as well as due to a lack of child-care (Maric, 2018; Bean et al., 2015).

However, gender disparities are not the only issue affecting individuals' involvement in the maker movement. Research (Seo, 2019; Stamos et al., 2019) also mentions the difficulties that people with disabilities face to participate in making activities. It is highlighted that accessibility problems drive the underrepresentation of this social group which has been generally marginalised in the maker movement. Among other, the common challenges that people with disabilities, especially blind makers, could face are inaccessible and undocumented instructions for the maker toolkits, less tangible design of the making board, and lack of multi-sensory modules. Finally, the literature discusses that underrepresented racial and ethnic minorities also seem to be less engaged in making activities. However, the reasons of this inclusion have not been addressed. Finally, as previously discussed, participation challenges are also faced by the elderly, people of lower education level, people with a lack of technical (STEM) skills, unemployed, and people of lower economic status.

3.6 Attitudes towards the maker movement

Regardless of the various barriers towards individuals' inclusion in making activities, the number of people involved in the maker movement has increased in the last decades (Kwon & Lee, 2017). Nevertheless, makers' insights and perspectives range. Recent reports demonstrate that participation in Makerspaces and the maker movement is mostly seen as a free-time activity that offers resourcefulness and empowerment (Rosa et al., 2018; Make & Intel, 2012). As such, makers gather in Makerspaces to spend time together with other people, share experiences, knowledge, and passion, and cultivate their hobbies. Furthermore, even though many of the participants see some opportunities for entrepreneurial development within Makerspaces, there are only a few cases whereby employment and its related benefits are real concerns or aspirations for the members of the maker communities. Besides that, among makers there is limited knowledge on how their individual maker projects can create meaningful impact (MAKE-IT project, 2017). Finally, it also seems that there is a considerable share of makers which aspires to remain small-scale and holds no desire to grow or sell their businesses, since they connect fast growth with overtaking personal skills, resources and values. Moreover, they believe that growth will influence their attachment to a place, as well their willingness to make a difference in local economies (Wolf-Powers et al., 2016). Overall, providing skills training, access to digital tools as well as technical support, seems to be the main goals for individuals who are involved in a Makerspace, whereas new employment opportunities, supporting of new creative tech

start-ups, promotion of the maker technology as well as a learning experience are not perceived as the main purpose of making initiatives.

4. Survey approach

4.1 Sample

The survey uses a quota sample including 6,420 responses from general public in 27 countries across Europe and Turkey. [While quota sampling is not representative of the general population, it was considered as a second-best next to random sampling, that was deemed infeasible due to lack of time and monetary resources.] Data collection took place from April 2020 to June 2020 through several waves, in order to monitor responses and ensure the structure and quality of the data. Instead of resource intensive methods such as computer-assisted-telephone-interviews (CATI) that would render data collection unduly expensive, to fill-in the quotas, responses were collected through online means via three channels. The first channel was crowdsourcing. This choice was selected as the most suitable to generate a large number of responses in a time- and cost-effective manner. In particular, the survey was administered in English using the crowdsourcing platforms Clickworker and Amazon MTurk. The choice of language was made on grounds of uniformity and considering the fact that the platforms' operating language is English it did not create bias towards persons with higher education credentials. Further to crowdsourcing, responses were collected through Pop Machina's website, mailing list, social media, and our partners' network in their respective countries (GR, BE, LT, NL, SP, TR). When disseminating through their own networks, partners used a native version of the questionnaire, which was uploaded to the EU Survey platform. Finally, to fill-in quotas for Lithuania and Turkey a native of version of the questionnaire was administered using the online panel of Dynata. Through these channels, data collection exceeded the initial goal of the task, generating circa 1,500 more responses than the benchmark target of 5,000 responses.

4.2 Questionnaire structure

The abovementioned sections reflect the main factors affecting stakeholders' acceptance levels, as they have been identified through the literature review process in Section 3. More details about the definition of the composite variables that have been used for our analysis are given in the following methodological section. The overall descriptive characteristics of the sample and the distribution of the collected responses are presented in Section 5.

To inform the items of the survey, we have conducted a literature review and submitted a draft version of the questionnaire to the consortium, for peer-review. The end-product reconciles - to the extent possible - the range of views and opinions from our partners and can be found on Appendix 1.

The survey's questions were clustered in 7 main sections, each of which corresponds to a research question. Each section and its rationale are presented briefly below:

1. **introduction to the topic:** this introductory, warm-up section, inquires participants about their knowledge on terms related to the maker movement;
2. **perceptions:** this section inquires participants about their thoughts on makerspaces;
3. **barriers:** the purpose of this section seeks to understand the main barriers hindering the general public from participating in makerspaces;
4. **motivations:** this section complements the barriers section through exploring why people would participate in a makerspace;

5. **willingness to join, openness and values:** this section inquires participants about value orientations to explain their beliefs towards environmental behaviour based on the findings of de Groot & Steg (2008). The section also considers future actions on behalf of the participants;
6. **environmental attitude:** this section uses a variation of a well-established scale to assess the participants' environmental attitude;
7. **general information:** this section includes basic demographic information such as sex, age, country, place or residence (e.g. urban or rural area), educational background, occupational status and others.

All demographic information was collected in compliance with the general data protection regulation (GDPR) of the European Union and used solely for research and statistical reasons. No natural person can be identified through their demographic information. In addition, to participate in the survey all research subjects had to fill-in a consent form that was included in the introductory session of the questionnaire. Finally, the management of datasets including such information adheres to the project's data management plan.

5. Analysis

5.1 Descriptive analysis

5.1.1 Demographics and main variables

This section presents the main findings regarding the descriptive characteristics of the sample and the responses that were collected throughout the large-scale survey. We aim at highlighting some initial findings regarding some general questions that were included in the survey. Starting from the spatial distribution of responses, Figure 1 shows the four main country groups that have been used for our analysis. These include 4 different clusters: Northern Europe (blue), Western Europe (yellow), Southern Europe (red) and Central - Eastern Europe (green).

Figure 1. Distribution of the collected responses at European level

The total number of responses varies for each group and is given in Table1. More specifically, the Western and Southern Europe have a significantly higher number of responses than Northern and Central Europe. The difference in participation may be due to higher levels of familiarisation and active involvement of more technologically developed countries to digital tools, such as crowdsourcing platforms. On the other hand, Northern Europe had the lowest representation in the survey by

number of responses. This can be explained by the fact that the northern cluster contained less countries with much fewer population living in this area than the rest of Europe. In the table below an analytical break down of the number of responses collected per country is presented.

Table 1. Sample distribution by country

	Country	Responses	Percentage
Central Eastern Europe	Bulgaria	13	0.20
	Croatia	10	0.16
	Czech Republic	105	1.64
	Hungary	111	1.73
	Poland	287	4.47
	Romania	209	3.26
	Slovak Republic	1	0.02
	Slovenia	2	0.03
	Central Eastern Europe total	738	11.50
Northern Europe	Denmark	64	1.00
	Estonia	7	0.11
	Finland	60	0.93
	Latvia	2	0.03
	Lithuania (*)	347	5.40
	Sweden	126	1.96
	Northern Europe total	606	9.44
Southern Europe	Cyprus	2	0.03
	Greece (*)	510	7.94
	Italy	642	10.00
	Malta	1	0.02
	Portugal	185	2.88
	Spain (*)	785	12.23
	Southern Europe total	2,125	33.10
Western Europe	Austria	190	2.96
	Belgium (*)	271	4.22
	France	696	10.84
	Germany	771	12.01
	Ireland	116	1.81
	Luxembourg	3	0.05
	Netherlands (*)	526	8.19
	Western Europe total	2,573	40.08
Non-EU countries	Turkey (*)	378	5.89
Total		6,420	100.00

* Pilot countries.

Source Authors' calculations

Moving one step further, Table 2 presents the breakdown of responses based on demographic characteristics. We can see that our sample is balanced in terms of gender (51.03% males - 46.43% females) and it follows an almost normal distribution considering age and educational level. As expected, persons between 25-39 years old are highly present in the sample (46.34%), together with individuals with tertiary education (66.70% - including all three tertiary education levels).

Table 2. Sample distribution by individual characteristics (gender, age, education and activity status)

Gender	Count	Percentage
Male	3276	51.03%
Female	2981	46.43%
Other	163	2.54%
Total	6420	100.00%

Age	Count	Percentage
18-24	1984	30.90%
25-29	1287	20.05%
30-39	1688	26.29%
40-49	939	14.63%
50-59	397	6.18%
60+	125	1.95%
Total	6420	100.00%

Education	Count	Percentage
No education	36	0.56%
Primary education	94	1.46%
Secondary education (lower)	310	4.83%
Secondary education (upper)	1698	26.45%
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	2792	43.49%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	1490	23.21%
Total	6420	100.00%

Activity status	Count	Percentage
Employed (full-time)	2740	42.68%
Employed (part-time)	767	11.95%
Unemployed	675	10.51%
Student	1691	26.34%
Household activity	221	3.44%
Retired	78	1.21%
Other	248	3.86%
Total	6420	100.00%

Source Authors' calculations

Figure 2. Previous experience with the maker movement

In terms of familiarity of the terms ‘maker movement’, ‘makerspace’, ‘circular economy’, ‘collaborative production’ and ‘sustainable urban development & regeneration’, the results indicate that despite the fact that only a small share (17.94%) of the respondents have previous experience with the maker movement (Figure 2), many of them are familiar with some of the provided terms, as shown in Figure 3. More specifically, the most well-known term is ‘sustainable urban development & regeneration’, as a significant share of the participants (39.53%) is moderately or extremely familiar with it (Figure 3). ‘Circular economy’ and ‘collaborative production’ seem to be slightly less-known terms among participants, as they indicate smaller shares of familiarity (31.14% and 32.71% respectively). Finally, both ‘maker movement’ and ‘makerspaces’ terms show the smallest familiarity levels amongst survey participants (17.93% and 19.17% respectively).

Figure 3. Levels of familiarity with terms related to the maker movement

A more detailed presentation of the results related to levels of familiarity is given in Table 3, illustrating results by individual characteristics' and country clusters breakdown. As we can see, there are significant differences between the four terms under investigation, as familiarity (both moderate and extreme) reaches a peak in all cases when referring to 'sustainable urban development & regeneration'. Moreover, there seems to be a difference between the European areas, specifically when comparing the case of Southern to Northern European countries. More specifically, Southern Europe indicates higher levels of familiarity in all focused terms, where its share is even 20 percentage points higher than the corresponding share of Northern EU countries (i.e. in the case of 'collaborative production' and 'sustainable urban development & regeneration'). At this point we need to stress that, large differences in the case of Non-EU countries (Turkey) might be because of sampling, as high share of participants are living in urban areas, as shown in Table 5. At the same time, there are no significant gender gaps in terms of familiarity, as shares of moderate or extreme familiar are similar between males and females. The same applies also in the case of age groups, as we can see that the highest detected difference is 9.29% between the 30-30 (41.29%) and 60+ (32%) age groups in the case of 'sustainable urban development & regeneration'.

On the contrary, education seems to significantly affect familiarity shares with the abovementioned terms. Although in the case of the terms 'maker movement' and 'makerspace' there seems to be a common understanding between the different educational levels, this picture changes a lot when we move on to the more general terms related to sustainability. More specifically, there is a large gap between persons with primary or no education and persons with tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent) as the difference between moderate/extreme familiarity shares is over 20% in the cases of 'circular economy' and 'sustainable urban development & regeneration' (21.07% and 26.54% respectively). Significant difference between these two educational groups also arises in the case of 'collaborative production' term (12.90%).

Finally, when focusing on the activity status groups, we can see that employed persons -either full-time or part-time- are the ones that have higher levels of familiarity with included terms. Of course, we should not ignore the increased shares in the case of students and persons involved in household activities that seem to be also highly informed about these terms. Unemployed and retired persons seem to be these activity status categories which are least familiar with the terms under investigation.

Table 3. Moderate and extreme familiarity shares (%) of key maker movement terms by spatial and individual characteristics (gender, age, education, and activity status)

	Maker movement	Makerspace	Circular economy	Collaborative production	Sustainable urban development & regeneration
Country clusters					
Central Eastern Europe	13.41%	14.23%	19.65%	25.34%	34.42%
Northern Europe	9.74%	12.87%	21.45%	19.14%	26.24%
Southern Europe	19.06%	18.92%	36.75%	39.34%	46.02%
Western Europe	14.34%	15.00%	28.72%	28.10%	34.01%
Non-EU countries (Turkey)	57.94%	68.78%	53.97%	62.96%	71.96%
Gender					
Male	19.28%	20.50%	31.75%	33.56%	39.31%
Female	16.37%	17.65%	30.43%	31.73%	39.79%
Age					
18-24	14.47%	14.92%	29.69%	32.26%	39.26%
25-29	17.79%	19.04%	31.39%	33.80%	40.17%
30-39	21.09%	21.50%	31.52%	34.06%	41.29%
40-49	18.53%	21.30%	31.84%	30.67%	37.38%
50-59	20.15%	24.94%	34.26%	31.49%	38.79%
60+	20.00%	22.40%	31.20%	29.60%	32.00%
Education					
Primary or no education	12.31%	15.38%	18.46%	23.08%	19.23%
Secondary education (lower)	18.71%	20.65%	20.65%	29.35%	33.55%
Secondary education (upper)	14.66%	16.43%	24.09%	27.39%	32.27%
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	19.52%	20.34%	32.70%	35.03%	42.23%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	18.99%	20.13%	39.53%	35.97%	45.77%
Activity status					
Employed (full-time)	22.30%	24.78%	35.29%	35.44%	42.12%
Employed (part-time)	17.60%	17.86%	25.81%	32.07%	38.46%
Unemployed	11.85%	11.70%	26.07%	27.70%	33.19%
Student	13.13%	13.31%	30.16%	31.40%	39.80%
Household activity	23.53%	22.17%	30.32%	33.03%	34.39%
Retired	19.23%	26.92%	25.64%	30.77%	28.21%
Other	14.52%	16.53%	24.60%	27.42%	37.90%
Total sample	17.93%	19.17%	31.14%	32.71%	39.53%

Note 1: All shares express the distribution within each category. This means that a 16.37% familiarity of the 'maker movement' term in women indicates that 16.37% of women are moderately or extremely familiar with this term.

Note 2: The large differences in the case of Non-EU countries (Turkey) might arise because of high share of participants living in urban areas as shown in Table 5.

Source Authors' calculations

An additional question related to experience was included in the large-scale survey to capture a more comprehensive overview of the current situation. Participants were asked to indicate whether they had previous experience with the maker movement. Results indicate that only a very small share of the participants had experience with the maker movement in the past (17.94%). Of course, this share seems to vary between different demographic groups. In general, persons between 30-39 years old indicate the highest share of experience (21.03%), alongside with employed and persons with household activity (21.50% and 21.72% respectively). The latter finding offers an interesting insight as it points out the close connection between not only job-related activities, but also household activities and the maker movement.

Table 4. Previous experience shares (%) by spatial and individual characteristics

Previous experience shares (%)	Yes	No	Total
Country clusters			
Central Eastern Europe	15.72%	84.28%	100.00%
Northern Europe	14.52%	85.48%	100.00%
Southern Europe	17.74%	82.26%	100.00%
Western Europe	15.55%	84.45%	100.00%
Non-EU countries (Turkey)	45.24%	54.76%	100.00%
Gender			
Male	19.02%	80.98%	100.00%
Female	16.71%	83.29%	100.00%
Age			
18-24	15.37%	84.63%	100.00%
25-29	19.11%	80.89%	100.00%
30-39	21.03%	78.97%	100.00%
40-49	17.04%	82.96%	100.00%
50-59	15.87%	84.13%	100.00%
60+	18.40%	81.60%	100.00%
Education			
Primary or no education	21.54%	78.46%	100.00%
Secondary education (lower)	19.03%	80.97%	100.00%
Secondary education (upper)	14.96%	85.04%	100.00%
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	18.66%	81.34%	100.00%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	19.46%	80.54%	100.00%
Activity Status			
Employed (full-time)	21.50%	78.50%	100.00%
Employed (part-time)	19.43%	80.57%	100.00%
Unemployed	13.33%	86.67%	100.00%
Student	13.72%	86.28%	100.00%
Household activity	21.72%	78.28%	100.00%
Retired	15.38%	84.62%	100.00%
Other	12.90%	87.10%	100.00%
Total sample	17.94%	82.06%	100.00%

Note: The large differences in the case of Non-EU countries (Turkey) might arise because of high share of participants living in urban areas as shown in Table 4.

Source Authors' calculations

Another interesting thing that we need to highlight is the relation between educational level and previous experience with maker movement. Figure 4 presents the distribution of the previous experience shares between the different educational levels. It becomes evident that persons reporting previous experience with the maker movement either indicate primary or no education, or tertiary education. This is an interesting finding as it provides evidence that activities related to the maker movement - given that they are mostly technical - may cover a wide range of technical expertise, starting from simple activities, that are related to low-skilled persons; and moving on to more advanced activities, that are closely relate to highly-skilled persons.

Figure 4. Shares (%) of previous experience with the maker movement by educational level

5.1.2 The role of urbanisation

As stated previously, an important aspect that needs to be considered during the analysis of the dataset is **the role of urban space** on the abovementioned factors. When looking at the previous results regarding the country clusters' analysis we can see that Turkey indicates significant variation when compared to all other EU country clusters. Hence, at this point it is essential to further explore the structure of the sample in terms of spatial typologies in order to investigate whether urbanisation plays a key role in the uptake of the maker movement, encompassing aspects of spillover effects and demographic composition, compared to semi-urban or rural areas. In this regard, Tables 5 and 6 present a preliminary descriptive analysis of the distribution of the answers related to the abovementioned variables in relation to different typologies, including urban, semi-urban and rural areas. More specifically, Table 5 illustrates the sample decomposition based on these three typologies pointing out the increased presence of people living in urban areas for the case of Turkey that might justify the variations in the results presented in the previous tables.

Table 5. Sample distribution (%) by typology

Typology	Urban	Semi-urban	Rural	Total
Total sample	40.19%	48.22%	11.59%	100.00%
Central-Eastern Europe	42,95%	46,48%	10,57%	100.00%
Northern Europe	24,75%	66,83%	8,42%	100.00%
Southern Europe	42,49%	48,28%	9,22%	100.00%
Western Europe	33,54%	50,29%	16,17%	100.00%
Non-EU countries (Turkey)	91,80%	7,41%	0,79%	100.00%

Note: Semi-urban areas include persons living in suburbs and towns.
Source Authors' calculations

At the same time, Table 6 indicates the distribution of familiarity and previous experience between the different typologies. As shown, there is a significant dominance of the urban centres as areas where people are more familiar with the terms of 'maker movement' and 'makerspace', alongside, of course, more common notions such as 'collaborative production', 'circular economy' and 'sustainable urban development & regeneration'. At the same time, participants living in urban areas also indicate increased previous experience with the maker movement, providing them with an advantage in terms of overall perception, awareness and willingness to join makerspaces, as we will see in the following sections of our analysis.

Table 6. Previous experience shares (%) by spatial and individual characteristics

	Urban	Semi-urban	Rural
Familiarity with terms (moderate or extreme)			
Maker movement	22.71%	15.21%	12.63%
Makerspace	25.04%	15.18%	15.46%
Circular economy	35.58%	28.46%	26.88%
Collaborative production	39.30%	28.49%	27.42%
Sustainable urban development & regeneration	46.78%	34.30%	36.16%
Previous experience with maker movement			
Yes	20.93%	16.47%	13.71%
No	79.07%	83.53%	86.29%

Source Authors' calculations

5.1.3 Types of activities and participation in makerspaces

Moving on, it is also interesting to take a closer look at the responses related to people's attitudes towards visiting or participating in a makerspace in their area (Q8). First, we can see that there is a strong positive attitude towards welcoming and inviting a makerspace in their region, as more than 70% (37.2% Agree – 35.2% Strongly agree) of the survey participants agree or strongly agree with this statement. At the same time, more than 60% of the participants would visit a makerspace in their area (37.4% Agree – 30.2% Strongly agree), whereas only 12,3% disagree with this statement (5.1% Strongly disagree – 7.2% Disagree). Finally, when it comes to more actual engagement regarding makerspaces, Figure 5 shows that over 60% (38.1% Agree – 24.7% Strongly agree) of the respondents indicated that they would use the facilities of a makerspace in their area.

Figure 5. Results regarding attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces (Q7)

In order to better understand the main type of activities that participants want to achieve through their participation in a makerspace we analyse the answers received in Q5_1 ('In what type of activities would you be interested in a maker community (e.g. a local workshop)?'). The following table presents the main findings at for the total sample, as well as the pilot countries. As we can see, the most popular activities related to makerspaces include photography, cinematography, and photo editing, as well as art and painting, whereas in the fourth place, we also find audio and visual production. This indicates that artistic activities are on the top of the list of activities that citizens aim to do when visiting a makerspace. Repairing consumer goods and software programming are two additional activities that have been found to be popular amongst respondents and are closely related to more professionally oriented perspectives. However, it is interesting to notice that 3D printing, which is also closely related to more professional applications lies in the last places of this list, whereas hardware and machinery have not received any votes.

Table 7. Types of activities that participants want to implement through their participation in makerspaces (Q5_1). Total sample and pilot countries

	Total sample	Belgium	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain	Turkey
Photography, cinematography, photo editing, etc.	15.31%	15.07%	15.04%	14.12%	14.30%	14.40%	10.76%
Art, painting, etc.	13.70%	10.51%	12.48%	11.57%	14.76%	14.08%	13.07%
Repair consumer goods	12.99%	10.40%	12.23%	9.80%	12.14%	12.81%	12.03%
Audio and visual production	10.82%	8.92%	9.54%	7.55%	9.23%	11.54%	8.61%
Woodworking, etc.	9.62%	9.02%	9.60%	8.73%	9.97%	8.69%	8.39%
Software programming, etc.	9.35%	11.57%	9.60%	6.18%	9.17%	7.58%	8.02%
Papercraft, origami, etc.	7.11%	5.63%	6.02%	6.08%	5.87%	7.54%	7.80%

	Total sample	Belgium	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain	Turkey
Sculpting, ceramics, etc.	6.43%	7.32%	3.97%	7.16%	6.38%	6.58%	5.35%
Metalworking, smithing, etc.	5.22%	5.20%	5.63%	4.71%	5.70%	4.24%	4.08%
Handcraft (e.g. bags, jewellery, knitting, sewing)	4.75%	6.79%	8.51%	13.04%	7.41%	6.55%	12.03%
Digital fabrication tools	1.96%	2.97%	2.69%	5.10%	2.91%	3.49%	4.16%
3D printing	0.99%	4.67%	3.07%	3.82%	0.57%	0.71%	3.79%
Hardware, machining, etc.	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
None of the above	1.16%	1.17%	0.83%	1.96%	1.03%	0.87%	1.34%
Other	0.59%	0.74%	0.77%	0.20%	0.57%	0.91%	0.59%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Note: EU-level results also include data from Turkey. Source: Authors' calculations.

The results presented in Table 7 indicate that it is important to investigate the nature of a makerspace that needs to be developed in an area, as it is essential to provide a solid orientation of the main activities that need to be achieved through it (either artistic or more manufacturing related). At the same time, it is important to invest in dissemination and communication of the offered activities in order for the citizens to be well informed about the existing potential of their local makerspaces and exploit its overall facilities in a way that would be beneficial to them and their community.

Apart from understanding the main activities that citizens wish to see included in a makerspace, it is also important to investigate their attitudes towards participation in makerspaces. When it comes to this, it is essential to better understand citizens' motives for participation. In this regard, Figure 6 presents the main outcomes related to ways in which citizens understand the role of makerspaces, either as a means to improve their skills and reach to new professional opportunities, or as a way to express their hobbies or help their local area. More specifically, in Figure 6 we can see that the vast majority of the respondents believe that their participation in makerspaces will provide them with benefits (Q7_1 – 60.58%) and will help them to improve their skills (Q7_2 – 79.64%). At the same time, a large share of the participants also agrees on the fact that their participation in makerspaces will have a positive impact on their region (Q7_3 – 71.79%) and will open professional opportunities (Q7_5 – 65.12%). Finally, many participants (49.85%) consider their participation in makerspaces as a hobby (Q7_4).

Figure 6. Results regarding perceptions for participating in makerspaces (Q7)

Q7_1: My participation in makerspaces will not provide any benefits to me.

Q7_2: My participation in makerspaces will improve my skills.

Q7_3: My participation in makerspaces will have a positive impact on my region.

Q7_4: My participation in makerspaces is something that I consider as a hobby.

Q7_5: My participation in makerspaces aims to open professional opportunities.

At the same time, Table 8 indicates the main reasons for joining a makerspace, as they have been identified through our large-scale survey including all participants. As we can see, learning new skills, developing new ideas and meeting individuals with common interests are the three most popular reasons for joining a makerspace, which are common in all cases. These are followed by aspects for improving employability skills, sharing knowledge and skills with others, and accessing tools or mentorship.

Table 8. Shares of replies (%) related to reasons for joining a makerspace (Q15_1). Total sample and pilot countries

	Total sample	Belgium	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain	Turkey
Learn new technical skills	15.19%	16.05%	14.45%	14.94%	15.65%	14.15%	12.21%
Develop ideas	12.77%	13.66%	12.85%	10.27%	12.05%	12.52%	13.34%
Meet individuals with common interests	10.80%	9.82%	11.08%	12.41%	12.09%	10.25%	8.88%
Improve my employability skills	9.42%	6.87%	6.52%	11.05%	8.78%	10.57%	9.46%
Share my knowledge and skills with others	9.32%	8.95%	9.85%	9.68%	8.62%	9.64%	10.18%
Access tools or mentorship	9.30%	11.26%	10.21%	6.95%	9.80%	8.44%	8.92%
Make new business contacts	8.31%	8.15%	8.40%	10.46%	7.43%	8.13%	9.33%
Promote sustainable development in my community	8.23%	9.58%	9.23%	6.63%	8.82%	9.03%	7.84%
Provide a valuable service to the community	8.14%	8.23%	9.67%	8.06%	8.42%	8.83%	11.40%
Learn how I could use my skills to setup a small business	7.79%	6.63%	7.28%	8.58%	7.56%	8.13%	7.80%
None of the above	0.65%	0.64%	0.40%	0.91%	0.69%	0.32%	0.54%
Other	0.08%	0.16%	0.07%	0.06%	0.08%	0.00%	0.09%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Source Authors' calculations

A more detailed analysis shedding light in the local specificities of our pilot cases is presented in the following sections. We follow the same approach, but we provide the results for each pilot specifically at a local level, so it can be seen in more detail how each case diversifies in terms of people's perceptions for participating or visiting makerspaces, as well as the main activities that they wish to perform through them.

5.1.4 Pilot cities

The following section provides a more detailed information regarding the pilot cities that have participated in the large-scale survey. We have analysed a set of variables for each city following the structure of the previous section, alongside the corresponding variables at a country level. We keep the analysis at a descriptive level, as more qualitative information at a local level needs to be collected in order to derive specific policy recommendations. However, our findings can be used as a valuable input for future workshops and discussion sessions that will be implemented in the pilot cities.

Each city section follows a similar structure. First, we present the main demographic distribution of the sample, alongside with shares referring to familiarity with relevant terms and previous experience with the maker movement. Second, we show the results for the attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces and the activities that participants would like to be included. Third, we provide information related to reasons for joining a makerspace, and finally, we present the results related to what people expect from their local community to do with regards to makerspaces.

5.1.4.1 Leuven (BE)

Starting with Leuven, we can see that the sample collected in this case includes 17 observations (Table 9). Most of the participants were men, 30-39 years old, employed and with tertiary education. With regards to familiarity with relevant terms, high scores have been achieved related to the maker movement and circular economy. Most of the participant have previous experience with the maker movement (70.59%), indicating that the sample has been very targeted to persons that have participated in activities related to makerspaces.

Table 9. Sample distribution for Belgium and Leuven by individual characteristics, familiarity and previous experience

	Belgium	Leuven
Gender		
Male	57.93%	64.71%
Female	42.07%	35.29%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Age		
18-24	49.08%	17.65%
25-29	19.19%	17.65%
30-39	19.93%	35.29%
40-49	9.59%	11.76%
50-59	1.48%	11.76%
60+	0.74%	5.88%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Education		
No education	0.37%	-
Primary education	1.48%	-
Secondary education (lower)	3.69%	-
Secondary education (upper)	23.99%	-
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	46.49%	17.65%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	23.99%	82.35%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Activity status		
Employed (full-time)	35.79%	64.71%
Employed (part-time)	7.75%	17.65%
Unemployed	5.90%	-
Student	45.39%	11.76%

	Belgium	Leuven
Household activity	1.85%	-
Retired	0.37%	5.88%
Other	2.95%	-
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Familiarity with terms (mean)		
Maker movement	2.07	4.00
Makerspace	2.12	4.06
Circular economy	2.82	4.41
Collaborative production	2.63	3.41
Sustainable urban development & regeneration	2.98	3.59
Previous experience with maker movement		
Yes	15.50%	70.59%
No	84.50%	29.41%
Total	100.00%	100.00%

Note: Belgium N=271 observations and Leuven N=17 observations.
Source Authors' calculations

Regarding previous experience, most survey participants from Leuven indicated that they have used makerspaces previously to develop a project (41.67%), as shown in Figure 7. Moreover, having a friend/acquaintance who is a maker or having participated in a maker activity constitute additional aspects for previous experience (16.67% in both cases), whereas only a very small percentage of them have just heard the maker movement (8.33%). This means that previous experience related to the case of Leuven refers to meaningful and on the field participation in makerspaces, and not just information related to makerspaces.

Figure 7. Sources of previous experience with the maker movement in Leuven (Q3_1)

In the case of attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces in Leuven, Figure 8 shows that in all cases -welcoming, visiting and using facilities- people are strongly positive. This strong agreement of course decreases as we move on to attitudes that require stronger engagement. In addition, our results shed light on the main types of activities that survey participants from Leuven want to do through their participation in makerspaces (Figure 9). More specifically, the top three activities include: (i) repair of consumer goods; (ii) woodworking, etc.; and (iii) 3D printing. It is interesting that 3D printing is on the top three choices, as in the overall sample it has been at the last places in the list (Table 6). Moreover, we can see that the first places on the list are mostly covered by manufacturing-related activities and not artistic.

Figure 8. Attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces in Leuven (Q7)

Figure 9. Types of activities that survey participants want to do through their participation in makerspaces in Leuven (Q5_1)

Figure 10 below presents the main reasons for joining a makerspace as they have been identified by people from Leuven. It becomes evident that mentorship, training on new technical skills and promotion of sustainable development are the main reasons for joining a makerspace.

Figure 10. Shares of replies (%) related to reasons for joining a makerspace in Leuven (Q15_1)

Figure 11. Proposed local community actions in Leuven (Q10)

In terms of local municipality interventions (Figure 11), participants from Leuven point out that increasing awareness about the contribution of the maker movement to sustainable urban development and regeneration is one of the most important things that their local municipality should do, as well as provide free access to makerspaces.

5.1.4.2 Thessaloniki and Piraeus (GR)

Table 10 presents the main sample distribution for Thessaloniki and Piraeus. As we can see, the sample for Piraeus includes 31 observations, whereas in the case of Thessaloniki, we can see that the sample is bigger (164 observations) offering a better distribution between the different demographic categories. In both cases, we can see that there is a gender balance, and for the case of Thessaloniki age distribution is also satisfactory. Most of the survey participants from these two cities have tertiary education and are employed.

Mean familiarity with terms related to the maker movement is low, following the overall country pattern. As expected, familiarity with terms related to circular economy, collaborative production and sustainable urban development & regeneration is higher in both cases compared to the two terms of the maker movement. Moreover, participants from Thessaloniki indicate an increased share of previous experience with the maker movement (15.85%), compared to the country share, whereas the same share is much lower for the case of Piraeus (3.23%).

Table 10. Sample distribution for Greece, Thessaloniki and Piraeus by individual characteristics (gender, age, education and activity status), familiarity and previous experience

	Greece	Thessaloniki	Piraeus
Gender			
Male	60.20%	51.83%	45.16%
Female	39.80%	48.17%	54.84%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Age			
18-24	20.59%	6.71%	-
25-29	21.96%	15.85%	6.45%
30-39	25.10%	23.78%	25.81%
40-49	22.94%	33.54%	41.94%
50-59	7.65%	17.07%	12.90%
60+	1.76%	3.05%	12.90%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Education			
No education	0.20%	-	-
Primary education	0.78%	-	-
Secondary education (lower)	1.57%	0.61%	-
Secondary education (upper)	18.82%	3.66%	3.23%
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	42.94%	34.15%	32.26%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	35.69%	61.59%	64.52%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Activity status			
Employed (full-time)	56.67%	76.83%	74.19%
Employed (part-time)	10.39%	4.88%	9.68%
Unemployed	9.02%	6.10%	-
Student	17.84%	8.54%	-
Household activity	2.35%	2.44%	-

	Greece	Thessaloniki	Piraeus
Retired	1.18%	1.21%	6.45%
Other	2.55%	-	9.68%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Familiarity with terms (mean)			
Maker movement	2.13	2.08	2.19
Makerspace	2.27	2.41	2.32
Circular economy	3.01	3.37	3.35
Collaborative production	2.96	3.02	2.84
Sustainable urban development & regeneration	3.15	3.39	3.23
Previous experience with maker movement			
Yes	11.37%	15.85%	3.23%
No	88.63%	84.15%	96.77%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Note: Greece N=510 observations, Thessaloniki N=164 and Piraeus N=31 observations.
Source Authors' calculations

Figure 12 shows that there is a strong positive attitude towards welcoming and visiting makerspaces in Thessaloniki (55.5% and 50.6% Strongly agree), however using their facilities receives a lower share of strong agreement (28%). A slightly different picture is formed in the city of Piraeus (Figure 13), where we can see that instead of strong agreement we have a more moderate approach towards welcoming (51.6% - Agree), visiting (51.6% - Agree) and using the facilities (58.1% - Agree) of makerspaces. In both cases there is a general positive attitude towards makerspaces.

Figure 12. Attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces in Thessaloniki (Q7)

Figure 13. Attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces in Piraeus (Q7)

In terms of activities, Figure 14 indicates that the most popular activities for the case of Thessaloniki are: (i) repair of consumer good; (ii) photography, cinematography, photo editing, etc.; (iii) wood-working, etc.; and (iv) art, painting, etc. The same also applies for the case of Piraeus (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Types of activities that survey participants want to do through their participation in makerspaces in Thessaloniki (Q5_1)

Figure 15. Types of activities that survey participants want to do through their participation in makerspaces in Piraeus (Q5_1)

Regarding the main reasons for joining the maker community, we can see that developing new ideas and learning new technical skills are two of the most important aspects (Figure 16 & 17). In the case of Piraeus, learning new technical skills exceeds all other choices. However, in the case of Thessaloniki meeting individuals with common interest can be found in the second place of the list, whereas in the case of Piraeus, providing valuable service to the community complete the top three reasons.

Figure 16. Shares of replies (%) related to reasons for joining a makerspace in Thessaloniki (Q15_1)

Figure 17. Shares of replies (%) related to reasons for joining a makerspace in Piraeus (Q15_1)

Finally, in terms of local municipality actions, Figure 18 & 19 indicate that survey participants expect that their municipalities should provide free access to makerspaces, increase awareness about the contribution of the maker movements to sustainable urban development and regeneration, as well as finance the development of makerspaces. Bringing together makers of the city to develop solutions related to existing challenges and providing non-financial incentives to boost participation are also highlighted by local participants. The results are very similar in both Thessaloniki and Piraeus.

Figure 18. Proposed local community actions in Thessaloniki (Q10)

Figure 19. Proposed local community actions in Piraeus (Q10)

5.1.4.3 Kaunas (LT)

In the case of Kaunas, the sample includes 15 observations. Table 11 shows that most of the survey participants have been males, 30-39 years old, employed and with higher education. Participants from Kaunas indicate lower levels of familiarity with terms relevant to the maker movement when compared to other pilot cities. However, terms related to circular economy and sustainable urban development are more familiar to them, as expected. Previous experience with the maker movement is also low (13.33%), but similar to other pilot cities.

Table 11. Sample distribution for Lithuania and Kaunas by individual characteristics (gender, age, education and activity status), familiarity and previous experience

	Lithuania	Kaunas
Gender		
Male	44.67%	40.00%
Female	55.33%	60.00%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Age		
18-24	14.12%	6.67%
25-29	14.99%	13.33%
30-39	25.36%	73.33%
40-49	17.87%	-
50-59	17.87%	6.67%
60+	9.80%	-
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Education		
No education	0.29%	-
Primary education	1.44%	-
Secondary education (lower)	-	-
Secondary education (upper)	14.70%	6.67%
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	33.43%	40.00%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	50.14%	53.33%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Activity status		
Employed (full-time)	63.98%	66.67%
Employed (part-time)	7.78%	20.00%
Unemployed	9.22%	-
Student	6.34%	6.67%
Household activity	4.32%	-
Retired	3.75%	-
Other	4.61%	6.67%
Total	100.00%	100.00%

	Lithuania	Kaunas
Familiarity with terms (mean)		
Maker movement	1.86	1.67
Makerspace	2.01	2.47
Circular economy	2.30	2.93
Collaborative production	2.40	2.13
Sustainable urban development & regeneration	2.55	2.73
Previous experience with maker movement		
Yes	15.56%	13.33%
No	84.44%	86.67%
Total	100.00%	100.00%

Note: Lithuania N=347 observations and Kaunas N=15 observations.
Source Authors' calculations

The results deriving from the question related to persons' attitudes towards future participation in makerspaces point out some interesting findings in the case of Kaunas that differ from all other pilot cases. More specifically, as we can see in Figure 20, participants express a strong disagreement in relation to visiting or using the facilities of a makerspace (66.7% and 53.3% respectively). This is completely in contrast with their strong positive attitudes towards welcoming and inviting a makerspace in their area (73.3%). This is a point that needs to be further investigated with more qualitative research exercises and probably interviews with local citizens, in order to investigate the reasons for this negative attitude towards visiting and actively participate in a makerspace.

Figure 20. Attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces in Kaunas (Q7)

Figure 21. Types of activities that survey participants want to do through their participation in makerspaces in Kaunas (Q5_1)

Figure 21 points out that persons aiming to participate in a makerspace find art, painting, etc. as the most popular activity that could attract their interest. Repair of consumer goods and sculpting, ceramics, etc. are two additional activities that gather a lot of attention, followed by handcraft, wood-working and metalworking activities. At the same time, meeting individuals with common interests and learning new technical skills are two important reasons that participants from Kaunas want to join a makerspace (Figure 22). These are followed by making new business contacts and sharing knowledge and skills with others.

Figure 22. Shares of replies (%) related to reasons for joining a makerspace in Kaunas (Q15_1)

In terms of targeted municipality actions, Figure 23 highlights that bringing together makers to develop solutions for the urban challenges, as well as providing non-financial incentives to makers for boosting participation are two essential actions that should be further considered.

Figure 23. Proposed local community actions in Kaunas (Q10)

5.1.4.4 Venlo (NL)

The sample coming from Venlo participants is an interesting case, as it contains 25 observations that mostly include male participants, over 30 years old, employed, with secondary and tertiary education (Table 12). Familiarity with terms related to the maker movement is increased compared to other pilot cities, as most of the terms indicate familiarity over 3. This of course derives as an outcome of the fact that a large share of the survey participants (48.00%) have previous experience with the maker movement. In this case, results for Venlo represent attitudes and opinions of experienced persons and makers.

Table 12. Sample distribution for the Netherlands and Venlo by individual characteristics (gender, age, education and activity status), familiarity and previous experience

	Netherlands	Venlo
Gender		
Male	48.67%	60.00%
Female	51.33%	40.00%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Age		
18-24	41.63%	4.00%
25-29	18.44%	4.00%
30-39	20.91%	20.00%
40-49	11.03%	16.00%
50-59	5.51%	20.00%
60+	2.47%	36.00%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Education		
No education	0.76%	-
Primary education	1.33%	-
Secondary education (lower)	3.42%	16.00%
Secondary education (upper)	28.52%	24.00%
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	49.24%	60.00%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	16.73%	-
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Activity status		
Employed (full-time)	31.18%	60.00%
Employed (part-time)	15.78%	20.00%
Unemployed	9.13%	-
Student	36.12%	4.00%
Household activity	2.28%	-
Retired	1.33%	16.00%
Other	4.18%	-
Total	100.00%	100.00%

	Netherlands	Venlo
Familiarity with terms (mean)		
Maker movement	1.93	3.12
Makerspace	1.91	3.12
Circular economy	2.87	3.56
Collaborative production	2.70	2.72
Sustainable urban development & regeneration	2.88	3.36
Previous experience with maker movement		
Yes	14.64%	48.00%
No	85.36%	52.00%
Total	100.00%	100.00%

Note: Netherlands N=526 observations and Venlo N=25 observations.
Source Authors' calculations

The following figure (Figure 24) confirms this argument as it shows that 25% of the participants have used a makerspace to develop a project, and another 25% have participated in a maker activity. This is essential information to know when trying to explain the outcomes of this survey for Venlo, as we should consider the fact that it reflects opinions of experienced people.

Figure 24. Sources of previous experience with the maker movement in Venlo (Q3_1)

As expected, attitudes towards welcoming, visiting and using the facilities of a makerspace are largely positive, as most of the participants would be open to these activities in their area (Figure 25). At the same time, the most popular activities that people in Venlo would like to do in a makerspace include: (i) art, painting, etc.; (ii) photography, cinematography, photo editing, etc.; and (iii) repairing of consumer goods (Figure 26). We also need to point out that the overall list of activities has been very balanced with very few differences between them.

Figure 25. Attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces in Venlo (Q7)

Figure 26. Types of activities that survey participants want to do through their participation in makerspaces in Venlo (Q5_1)

As shown in Figure 27, the main reasons for joining a makerspace in Venlo focus on: (i) developing new ideas; (ii) promoting sustainable development in the local community; and (iii) sharing new knowledge and skills with others. The least important reasons refer to making new business contacts and improving employability skills.

Figure 27. Shares of replies (%) related to reasons for joining a makerspace in Venlo (Q15_1)

Providing free access to makerspaces is the most important local community action in Venlo (Figure 28), followed by action for bringing together city makers to develop solutions and increasing awareness regarding the contribution of the maker movement on sustainable urban development.

Figure 28. Proposed local community actions in Venlo (Q10)

5.1.4.5 Santander (ES)

In the case of Santander, we have a sample of 30 observations which is balanced in terms of gender and age distribution, covering all existing categories. However, most participants have received tertiary education and are employed. Again, as in the case of Venlo, we can see that persons who participated in this local survey process are very familiar with all terms related to the maker movement (mean familiarity over 3) and a large share of them has previous experience with it (43.33%) (Table 13).

Table 13. Sample distribution for Spain and Santander by individual characteristics (gender, age, education and activity status), familiarity and previous experience

	Spain	Santander
Gender		
Male	48.92%	56.67%
Female	51.08%	43.33%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Age		
18-24	25.10%	3.33%
25-29	21.27%	3.33%
30-39	25.48%	16.67%
40-49	21.02%	43.33%
50-59	5.86%	23.33%
60+	1.27%	10.00%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Education		
No education	0.64%	-
Primary education	1.66%	-
Secondary education (lower)	18.60%	-
Secondary education (upper)	54.65%	20.00%
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	24.46%	40.00%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	0.64%	40.00%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Activity status		
Employed (full-time)	38.47%	60.00%
Employed (part-time)	17.07%	-
Unemployed	17.07%	20.00%
Student	21.53%	-
Household activity	2.42%	-
Retired	0.51%	-
Other	2.93%	20.00%
Total	100.00%	100.00%

	Spain	Santander
Familiarity with terms (mean)		
Maker movement	2.48	3.70
Makerspace	2.41	3.40
Circular economy	3.14	3.83
Collaborative production	3.27	3.70
Sustainable urban development & regeneration	3.39	3.77
Previous experience with maker movement		
Yes	23.95%	43.33%
No	76.05%	56.67%
Total	100.00%	100.00%

Note: Spain N=785 observations and Santander N=30 observations.
Source Authors' calculations

Figure 29. Sources of previous experience with the maker movement in Santander (Q3_1)

Given that in the case of Santander we have a sample of experienced participants, it makes sense to further investigate the main sources from which they have encountered the maker movement. Figure 29 indicates that most of the participants have used a makerspace to develop a project (30.77%) or have participated in a maker activity directly (38.46%), and only a small share of them had just a friend who is a maker (15.38%) and brought them in contact with the maker movement.

In terms of attitudes towards makerspaces, Figure 30 shows that there is a strong positive feeling from the survey participants in Santander for welcoming, inviting, visiting and using the facilities of a makerspace, indicating an overall increased interest for being actively involved in the activities of the maker movement. In relation to this, we can see that the makerspace activities that are the most popular in Santander include: (i) repair of consumer goods; (ii) 3D printing; and (iii) digital fabrication tools. It is interesting that both 3D printing and digital fabrication tools are less popular in almost all other cases, including the total EU-level sample. However, we can see that Santander seems to have

a core of makers and potential participants that are interested in these activities which are closely related to production processes. Artistic activities are found in the following places of the list.

Figure 30. Attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces in Santander (Q7)

Figure 31. Types of activities that survey participants want to do through their participation in makerspaces in Santander (Q5_1)

Taking a closer look at the reasons motivating survey participants in Santander to join a makerspace (Figure 32), we can see that promoting sustainable development in the local community lies at the top place. Moreover, learning new skills, providing valuable service to the community, and sharing knowledge and skills with other people constitute three additional reasons for joining a makerspace in Santander. In this regard, survey participants have highlighted that bringing together makers of Santander to develop solutions related to existing local challenges is the top suggested action to the local municipality, as shown in Figure 33. Providing free access to makerspaces is in this case less important as all other suggested actions, as it is found in the last place.

Figure 32. Shares of replies (%) related to reasons for joining a makerspace in Santander (Q15_1)

Figure 33. Proposed local community actions in Santander (Q10)

5.1.4.6 Istanbul (TR)

The sample coming from Istanbul includes 22 observations balanced in terms of gender. Moreover, most participants are between 30-49 years old, employed and all of them with tertiary education (Table 14). Familiarity with terms related to the maker movement is increased compared to other pilot cities and the overall sample, as for most terms familiarity is over 3. Although there seems to be an increased familiarity with relevant terms, people who participated in this survey have not previous experience with the maker movement to a large extent (22.73%), but instead, they have an indirect connection with it through a friend or acquaintance who is a maker (60%) (Figure 34).

Table 14. Sample distribution for Turkey and Istanbul by individual characteristics (gender, age, education and activity status), familiarity and previous experience

	Turkey	Istanbul
Gender		
Male	50.26%	45.45%
Female	49.74%	54.55%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Age		
18-24	15.87%	-
25-29	12.43%	9.09%
30-39	34.39%	54.55%
40-49	19.84%	31.82%
50-59	13.49%	4.55%
60+	3.97%	-
Total	100.00%	100.00%

	Turkey	Istanbul
Education		
No education	0.26%	-
Primary education	0.79%	-
Secondary education (lower)	16.40%	-
Secondary education (upper)	10.32%	-
Tertiary education (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	58.73%	59.09%
Tertiary education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)	13.49%	40.91%
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Activity status		
Employed (full-time)	62.17%	100.00%
Employed (part-time)	6.08%	-
Unemployed	6.08%	-
Student	11.11%	-
Household activity	8.47%	-
Retired	5.03%	-
Other	1.06%	-
Total	100.00%	100.00%
Familiarity with terms (moderate or extreme)		
Maker movement	3.60	3.18
Makerspace	3.87	3.82
Circular economy	3.54	3.73
Collaborative production	3.74	3.55
Sustainable urban development & regeneration	3.99	3.64
Previous experience with maker movement		
Yes	45.24%	22.73%
No	54.76%	77.27%
Total	100.00%	100.00%

Note: Turkey N=378 observations and Istanbul N=22 observations.
Source Authors' calculations

Figure 34. Sources of previous experience with the maker movement in Istanbul (Q3_1)

Figure 35 shows that there is an overall positive attitude towards welcoming, visiting and using the facilities of a makerspace, and only a very small share of persons would be negative on participating somehow in makerspaces (4.5% for visiting and 4.5% for using the facilities). At the same time, art, painting, etc. are the top activities that participants from Istanbul would like to do when visiting a makerspace, followed by repair of consumer goods, handcraft and photography, cinematography, photo editing, etc. 3D printing and hardware are places very low in the overall list of activities (Figure 36). Finally, when it comes to reasons for joining a makerspace, learning new technical skills is the top reason proposed by the survey participants, with developing new ideas and providing valuable service to the community lying in the next two places of the list (Figure 37).

Figure 35. Attitudes towards visiting or participating in makerspaces in Istanbul (Q7)

Figure 36. Types of activities that survey participants want to do through their participation in makerspaces in Istanbul (Q5_1)

Figure 37. Shares of replies (%) related to reasons for joining a makerspace in Istanbul (Q15_1)

5.2 Factor analysis

The next two sections of this report include a detailed presentation of the methods that have been used for further exploring the collected data, in order to get through insights for the factors affecting perceptions and participation in the maker movement. For this reason, we have used a two-step approach that includes first, a factor analysis in order to identify the most essential factors that result by combining the different items for a specific set of questions, and second, an ordered logit model that reveals the main factors affecting general public perceptions and willingness to join.

Factor analysis is a variable reduction process that aims at revealing relationships between several variables within a dataset. Its main goal is to identify clusters of variables that can be jointly used to proxy specific dimensions of the analysis. In our case, we have structured the Pop-Machina survey in a way that each dimension that we want to explore more thoroughly consists of a set of related items that try to capture different parts of this dimension. More specifically, Table 15 indicates the questions and their individual items that have been used for factor analysis to calculate dimensions that we want to consider for our statistical analysis in the next step. Each one of the following questions refers to a specific dimension.

We perform a factor analysis for each of the abovementioned questions, to build our composite variables referring to these dimensions. The results in each case are given below (Tables 16-21) and include all 6,420 participants who have answered the indicated likert-scale questions. For each of the corresponding questions we have highlighted the values that belong to each factor

Table 15. Structure of questions and their relevant items that have been used for factor analysis

Question	Items
Q9 - I would like makerspaces to:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance skills and improve the employability of local community members. Act as open places for discussion about our community concerns. Generate solutions for the local challenges of my community. Empower local citizens to become more sensitive about environmental sustainability. Involve vulnerable groups (e.g. migrants, elderly, people with disabilities, etc.). Contribute to lowering the environmental footprint of my city/country. Remain in a small-scale operation and contribute towards their local community's economy. Scale-up their production and contribute towards a more circular economy across Europe.
Q11 - Regarding my participation in a makerspace, I am concerned about the following aspects:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low participation rate. Lack of the necessary time to join. Lack of knowledge on how to start. Lack of knowledge on where to go. Lack of information about makerspaces and their actions. Lack of financial incentives to support it and its development. Lack of the necessary technical skills and no tutoring available for assistance. No physical space available that would fit the needs of such maker community. Lack of proper health and safety regulations and clarity about responsibility in case of an accident.
Q13 - I would like to join a makerspace but:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I do not know if there is a makerspace in my region. There are no makerspaces in my region. I am not sure if I have the right skills. I have concerns about my age. I feel that my gender is not equally represented.

Question	Items
Q18 - To what extent do you agree with the following statements?	<p>I do not like trying new things and would rather stick with what I know.</p> <p>I try to learn something new every day.</p> <p>I understand that people can have different attitudes toward certain things than I do.</p> <p>I am open towards listening what others have to say.</p> <p>I learn a great deal from people with differing beliefs.</p> <p>I feel that an opportunity to learn about the cultures of others is something to be treasured.</p>
Q19 - How important are the following aspects for you?	<p>Equality: equal opportunity for all</p> <p>Social justice: correcting injustice, care for the weak</p> <p>Being helpful: working for the welfare of others</p> <p>Respecting the earth: harmony with other species</p> <p>Unity with nature: fitting into nature</p> <p>Protecting the environment: preserving nature</p> <p>Wealth: material possessions, money</p> <p>Authority: the right to lead or command</p> <p>Influence: having an impact on people and events</p>
Q20 - To what extent do you agree with the following statements?	<p>Humans have the right to modify the natural environment to suit their needs.</p> <p>Human ingenuity will ensure that we do not make the Earth unlivable.</p> <p>The balance of nature is strong enough to cope with the impacts of modern industrial nations.</p> <p>The so-called 'ecological crisis' facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated.</p> <p>Humans were meant to rule over the rest of nature.</p> <p>Humans will eventually learn enough about how nature works to be able to control it.</p> <p>When humans interfere with nature it often produces disastrous consequences.</p> <p>Humans are seriously abusing the environment.</p> <p>The Earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them.</p> <p>Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist.</p> <p>Despite our special abilities, humans are still subject to the laws of nature</p> <p>If things continue on their present course, we will soon experience a major ecological catastrophe.</p> <p>We are approaching the limit of the number of people the Earth can support.</p> <p>The Earth is like a spaceship with very limited room and resources.</p> <p>The balance of nature is very delicate and easily upset.</p>

In Q9 we can see that all items included in the question are part of a sole factor, capturing its various dimensions. However, in most of the other cases there are more than one factors rising from each question, referring to different aspects of a more general umbrella theme. The derived factors constitute the baseline upon which we build our ordered logit model in the next step of our analysis. More specifically, Q9 refers to the identification of the main drivers for boosting the maker movements and participation to makerspaces. This is indeed one of the core questions included in the large-scale survey providing significant inputs in terms of policy design. As we can see, the factor analysis results indicate that all items included on our survey in this question can form a single factor. This refers to the role of makerspaces as means for: (i) enhancing skills and employability; (ii) empowering local community discussions, solutions, and inclusion; and (iii) boosting circular economy and environmental sustainability. In this case, citizens' participation, collaboration between makers and local businesses, as well as initiatives supported by local communities, organisations and companies and actions for improving local community image are included in this factor. Factor analysis indicates that all items are part of a general dimension related to drivers (Table 16).

Table 16. Rotated component loading for drivers including 8 items

Q9 – Items	Factor 1
Enhance skills and improve the employability of local community members	0.783
Remain in a small-scale operation and contribute towards their local community's economy	0.498
Act as open places for discussion about our community concerns	0.744
Generate solutions for the local challenges of my community	0.807
Involve vulnerable groups (e.g. migrants, elderly, people with disabilities, etc.)	0.740
Contribute to lowering the environmental footprint of my city/country	0.777
Empower local citizens to become more sensitive about environmental sustainability	0.817
Scale-up their production and contribute towards a more circular economy across Europe	0.640
Eigenvalues	4.292
Variance	4.292
Number of test items included	8

Source Authors' calculations

Alongside the previous questions, Q11 tries to shed light on the main barriers that individuals consider to be important for participation in makerspaces. Using factor analysis, we can identify three main types of barriers related to: (i) **individual** lack of knowledge and information on how to participate; (ii) **makerspace-related** lack of information regarding the ways citizens can exploit the opportunities offered by them; and (iii) general **operational characteristics** of the makerspaces, such as space and health and safety regulations. The items shaping each factor are shown in Table 17.

Table 17. Rotated component loading for barriers to participate including 9 items

Q11 – Items	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Low participation rate	0.558	-0.005	0.422
Lack of the necessary time to join	0.677	-0.027	0.265
Lack of knowledge on how to start	0.806	0.308	-0.009
Lack of knowledge on where to go	0.769	0.282	0.061
Lack of information about makerspaces and their actions	0.260	0.735	0.045
Lack of financial incentives to support it and its development	0.142	0.789	0.102
Lack of the necessary technical skills and no tutoring available for assistance	0.190	0.638	0.291
No physical space available that would fit the needs of such maker community	0.085	0.102	0.802
Lack of proper health and safety regulations and clarity about responsibility in case of an accident	0.080	0.144	0.791
Eigenvalues	3.286	1.206	1.049
Variance	2.150	1.774	1.617
Number of test items included	4	3	2

Source Authors' calculations

As an addition to the previous question, we also wanted to capture barriers for joining in the form of concerns from an individual perspective. In this case, the factor analysis results indicate that Q13 can be splitted into two factors, as shown in Table 18. One related to the lack of knowledge regarding the presence or not of a makerspace in a region, alongside with doubts whether the individual has

the right skills; whereas the second factor refers to the perception that demographic characteristics might affect negatively participation in makerspaces.

Table 18. Rotated component loading for barriers to join including 5 items

Q13 – Items	Factor 1	Factor 2
I do not know if there is a makerspace in my region.	0.838	-0.066
There are no makerspaces in my region.	0.828	0.091
I am not sure if I have the right skills.	0.573	0.440
I have concerns about my age.	0.084	0.852
I feel that my gender is not equally represented.	-0.012	0.865
Eigenvalues	2.036	1.368
Variance	1.723	1.680
Number of test items included	3	2

Source Authors' calculations

At the same time, we followed a similar process to investigate the main items related to the question of openness (Q18). The items included in this question reflect the personality of a person towards being open to new experiences and challenges, which might be highly related to its willingness to participate and join the maker movement. The results for the identification of these dimensions are given in Table 19.

Table 19. Rotated component loading for openness including 6 items

Q18 – Items	Factor 1
I don't like trying new things and would rather stick with what I know.	-0.391
I try to learn something new every day.	0.662
I understand that people can have different attitudes toward certain things than I do.	0.716
I am open towards listening what others have to say.	0.816
I learn a great deal from people with differing beliefs.	0.788
I feel that an opportunity to learn about the cultures of others is something to be treasured.	0.779
Eigenvalues	2.998
Variance	2.998
Number of test items included	6

Source Authors' calculations

Finally, the last two questions aim at capturing some of the main environmental values and attitudes of the participants to investigate the ways in which they affect the formation of perceptions of individuals regarding makerspaces. It is essential to highlight that in both cases we used a well-targeted set of items to identify those individual beliefs, considering also the limited extend of the questionnaire. In the first case, we used part of the proposed Schwartz Value Survey items for measuring environmental beliefs (Schwartz, 2003; Steg et al., 2014; Bouman et al., 2018), by selecting a set of items to form three dimensions related to: biospheric, altruistic and egoistic values. The factor analysis revealed these discrete areas, with the altruistic and biospheric values being grouped in the same factor, as presented in Table 20.

Table 20. Rotated component loading for environmental values including 9 items

Q19 – Items	Factor 1 Altruistic & Biospheric	Factor 2 Egoistic
Equality: equal opportunity for all	0.797	0.049
Social justice: correcting injustice, care for the weak	0.807	0.053
Being helpful: working for the welfare of others	0.785	0.112
Respecting the earth: harmony with other species	0.854	0.067
Unity with nature: fitting into nature	0.794	0.107
Protecting the environment: preserving nature	0.842	0.065
Wealth: material possessions, money	0.049	0.769
Authority: the right to lead or command	-0.015	0.875
Influence: having an impact on people and events	0.244	0.753
Eigenvalues	4.184	1.813
Variance	4.035	1.962
Number of test items included	6	3

Source Authors' calculations

Secondly, we used the New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) scale for assessing environmental attitudes (Rosa et al., 2018; Amburgey & Thoman, 2012; Albrecht et al., 1982). The results of Q20 indicate that the items included in this question can be grouped into 5 discrete factors, which in some cases encompass multiple aspects of the NEP scale (Table 20). More specifically, we can see that: (i) Factor 1 includes items from ecocrisis and human domination aspects; (ii) Factor 2 covers balance of nature, antiexemptionalism and human domination; (iii) Factor 3 refers only to balance of nature; (iv) Factor 4 focuses solely on limits to growth; and (v) Factor 5 refers to ecocrisis, antiexemptionalism and limits to growth. The derived results enable us to construct these three factors for including them into our logit model in the next step of the analysis.

Table 21. Rotated component loading for NEP scale including 15 items

Q20 – Items	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5
Balance of nature					
The balance of nature is strong enough to cope with the impacts of modern industrial nations. (R)	-0.288	-0.629	-0.122	-0.265	-0.121
When humans interfere with nature it often produces disastrous consequences.	0.400	0.341	0.540	0.071	0.334
The balance of nature is very delicate and easily upset.	0.041	0.147	-0.851	-0.020	-0.099
Ecocrisis					
The so-called 'ecological crisis' facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated. (R)	0.804	0.199	0.080	0.177	0.063
Humans are seriously abusing the environment.	0.093	0.351	0.304	-0.011	0.519
If things continue on their present course, we will soon experience a major ecological catastrophe.	0.536	0.377	0.505	0.162	-0.071

Q20 – Items	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5
Antiexemptionalism					
Human ingenuity will ensure that we do not make the earth unlivable. (R)	0.071	0.747	-0.249	-0.056	-0.114
Humans will eventually learn enough about how nature works to be able to control it. (R)	0.161	0.782	0.002	0.180	-0.068
Despite our special abilities, humans are still subject to the laws of nature	-0.009	-0.017	0.235	0.096	0.806
Limits to growth					
The earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them. (R)	-0.095	0.369	0.249	0.225	-0.652
We are approaching the limit of the number of people the earth can support.	0.094	0.105	-0.027	0.889	-0.031
The earth is like a spaceship with very limited room and resources.	0.098	0.031	0.495	0.661	0.081
Human domination					
Humans have the right to modify the natural environment to suit their needs. (R)	0.438	0.586	0.200	-0.022	-0.019
Humans were meant to rule over the rest of nature. (R)	0.822	0.181	-0.181	0.149	-0.011
Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist.	0.682	-0.088	0.280	-0.417	0.108
Eigenvalues	4.352	2.1357	1.666	1.086	1.017
Variance	2.577	2.540	1.960	1.655	1.526
Number of test items included	4	4	2	2	3

Note: NEP = New Ecological Paradigm. (R) indicates reverse-scored items from the scale.
Source Authors' calculations

5.3 Statistical analysis

This section includes the statistical analysis of the data that were collected throughout the large-scale survey in this task. To estimate the effects of selected parameters on general public perceptions and willingness to participate in the maker movement measured in a 5-point likert scale, we have developed and estimated an ordered logic model.

Following Long and Freese (2006), the ordinal regression model is commonly presented as a latent variable model. In this context, we define y^* as a latent variable ranging from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$, and thus, the structural model is given in eq. (1).

$$y_i^* = \mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where y_i^* is the exact but unobserved dependent variable for observation i ; \mathbf{x} is the vector of independent variables; ε_i is the error term, and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the vector of regression coefficients which we target on estimating. In the case of ordered logit models, we cannot observe y_i^* , but instead we have only observations for the categories of response. In our case, the measurement model for ordinal outcomes is expanded to divide y_i^* into 5 ordinal categories:

$$y_i = m \text{ if } \tau_{m-1} \leq y_i^* \leq \tau_m \text{ for } m = 1 \text{ to } 5$$

Where the thresholds τ_1 through τ_5 are estimated. The probability of an observed outcome for a given set of values of the independent variables of \mathbf{x}_i^T corresponds to the area of the distribution where y_i^* falls between τ_{m-1} and τ_m as given below:

$$Pr(y = m | \mathbf{x}) = Pr(\tau_{m-1} \leq y_i^* \leq \tau_m | \mathbf{x})$$

In our case, we choose to use a set of two dependent variables including aspects of perceptions related to the maker movement and willingness to join makerspaces. It is important to notice that we have used the factor analysis results presented in the previous section as explanatory variables (IVs) in our models. Below, we present the list of variables that have been used for our analysis.

IVs	Short description	Related question
Positive perception about CE	Agreement level for positive perception for circular economy	Q6_2
Familiarity with terms	Overall familiarity with terms related to the maker movement	Q1_1 – Q1_5
Previous experience	Dummy indicating previous experience with the maker movement	Q2
Like to repair or make things	Dummy indicating whether the respondent likes to repair or make things	Q4
Negative impacts	Overall perception of the respondent regarding the relation of the makerspaces to negative impacts	Q12_1 – Q12_4
Drivers	Factor for participation drivers	Q9 – Table 16
Barriers to participate_F1	Factor 1 for participation barriers	Q11 – Table 17
Barriers to participate_F2	Factor 2 for participation barriers	
Barriers to participate_F3	Factor 3 for participation barriers	
Barriers to join_F1	Factor 1 for barriers to join	Q13 – Table 18
Barriers to join_F2	Factor 2 for barriers to join	
Concerns about ethnic background*	Dummy for indicating concern for ethnic background as a barrier to join a makerspace	Q13_4
Certificate	Dummy indicating that certificate is a motive for joining a makerspace	Q16
Openness	Factor for openness	Q18 – Table 19
Openness – ethnic diversity*	Dummy for indicating that the individual is open to ethnic diversity	Q18_6
Altruistic & biospheric values	Factor 1 for environmental values (altruistic and biospheric values)	Q19 – Table 20
Egoistic values	Factor 2 for environmental values (egoistic values)	
NEP_F1	Factor 1 for NEP scale	Q20 – Table 21
NEP_F2	Factor 2 for NEP scale	
NEP_F3	Factor 3 for NEP scale	
NEP_F4	Factor 4 for NEP scale	
NEP_F5	Factor 5 for NEP scale	
Gender	Dummy for females	Q21
Education	Educational level in year of schooling	Q25
Age	Age	Q22
Urban areas	Dummy for urban areas	Q24
Rural areas	Dummy for rural areas	
Central Eastern Europe	Dummy for Central Eastern European countries	Q23
Southern Europe	Dummy for Southern European countries	
Northern Europe	Dummy for Northern European countries	
Non-EU countries (Turkey)	Dummy for Non-European countries	

* These questions were not included in the Turkish version of the questionnaire.

The results of the analysis for the two models that we run for the overall sample are presented in Table 22, whereas the country-specific analysis results are given in Tables 23 and 24. As it is shown, most of the identified variables included in our model have been found to be statistically significant when related to the overall perceptions and willingness to join, which we use as our dependent variables. By taking a closer look at the results, we can see that positive perceptions about circular economy (CE), familiarity with terms related to the maker movement and previous experience constitute significant parameters positively affecting both our dependent variables. In the first case, **positive attitude towards CE** (Q6_2 – ‘My overall perception about circular economy is positive’) has been found statistically significant in all cases when referring to maker movement perceptions, but instead, it is not significant when related to willingness to join a makerspace. Secondly, **familiarity with the terms that are closely related to the maker movement** (as described in Table 3) is also a significant parameter that positively affects in almost all cases (apart from the case of the Netherlands) both perceptions and willingness to join makerspaces.

At the same time, **previous experience** refers to Q2 (‘Do you have previous experience with the maker movement?’) and captures real experience related to the maker movements and makerspaces. This parameter is statistically significant both for perception and willingness to join when we take the total EU level and Turkey sample, meaning that higher levels of previous experience result in more positive perceptions and acceptance. However, the results differ when we take a closer look at the specific countries under investigation. Especially for the case of Belgium, previous experience seems to negatively affect willingness to join makerspaces, whereas it does not affect overall perceptions. For the Netherlands it affects positively overall perceptions about makerspaces, whilst for Spain and Greece it is positive and statistically significant referring to willingness to join. Finally, results did not show any statistically significance for the case of Lithuania and Turkey.

When we move on to **Q4** (‘Do you consider yourself a person who likes to repair or make things?’) we can see that this variable indicates a positive impact on perception and willingness to join in almost all cases. Moreover, **perceptions related to potentially negative impacts** arising from makerspaces captured through Q12 (Q12_1-Q12_4) have been found to be statistically significant and with a negative effect as expected. On the contrary, results indicate that the factor related to the main **drivers** (Q9) as it has been defined from Section 5.2 (Table 16) positively affects perceptions and willingness to join in almost all cases. At the same time, factors related to **barriers** -both for participating and joining makerspaces- are statistically significant only in some cases, without indicating any specific patterns. The variable related to **potential concerns about ethnic background** (Q13_4 – ‘I would like to join a makerspace but I feel that I do not fit in due to my ethnic background.’) is statistically significant only for the total sample and the case of Spain negatively affecting both overall perceptions and willingness to join makerspaces. The **provision of a certificate** (Q16) is another significant variable that acts as a driver for joining makerspaces in most cases (total sample, Netherlands, Spain, Lithuania and Turkey).

In terms of individual characteristics, the results indicate that **openness** (Q18) is a significant characteristic that positively affects mostly willingness to join makerspaces (total sample, Netherlands, Spain and Turkey). At the same time, **openness to ethnic diversity** (Q18_6) is statistically significant only at the total EU level and not in the specific countries we investigate. The factor encompassing **altruistic and biospheric values**, as it has been defined from Section 5.2 (Table 20) is another parameter that positively affects both overall perceptions and willingness to join (mostly the latter one at the country level), whereas **egoistic values** have not been found statistically significant at all. In terms of **environmental beliefs**, only some of the factors deriving from the NEP scale identified in Table 21 indicate a significant effect without any specific pattern between the samples.

Finally, when it comes to **demographic characteristics**, we can see that **gender** and **age** are the ones mostly affecting perceptions and willingness to join, with **education** being significant in only two country cases (Belgium and Spain). When we look at the overall sample, it is interesting to notice that being a woman positively affects the overall perception for makerspaces, but it has a negative

impact on willingness to join makerspaces. We find a different pattern in the case of Lithuania where women are also less positive towards makerspaces. In the case of age, we can see that younger persons tend to have more positive perceptions regarding makerspaces, whereas older persons are more willing to join them. Finally, **spatial characteristics** referring to the type of the area where the participants reside have not been found significant in any of the cases.

Table 22. Ordered logit model results for total sample (EU level and Turkey)

IVs	Perceptions		Willingness to join	
	Coefficient		Coefficient	
Positive perception about CE	1.101	***	0,060	*
Familiarity with terms	0.035	***	0,050	***
Previous experience	0.211	***	0,358	***
Like to repair or make things	0.200	***	0,656	***
Negative impacts	-0.046	***	-0,030	***
Drivers	0.723	***	0,616	***
Barriers to participate_F1	0.010		-0,169	***
Barriers to participate_F2	0.042		0,032	
Barriers to participate_F3	-0.081	***	-0,037	
Barriers to join_F1	0.064	*	0,153	***
Barriers to join_F2	-0.066	*	-0,029	
Concerns about ethnic background	-0.105	***	0,062	**
Certificate	0.010		0,209	***
Openness	0.323	***	0,649	***
Openness – ethnic diversity	0.017		0,079	**
Altruistic & biospheric values	0.273	***	0,324	***
Egoistic values	-0.013		-0,032	
NEP_F1	-0.036		-0,044	
NEP_F2	-0.049		0,022	
NEP_F3	0.012		0,005	
NEP_F4	0.021		-0,012	
NEP_F5	0.133	***	-0,031	
Gender	0.248	***	-0,114	**
Education	-0.007		0,004	
Age	-0.050	**	0,051	**
Urban areas	-0.057		0,067	
Rural areas	-0.049		0,014	
CE Europe	0.230	**	0,363	***
Southern Europe	-0.003		-0,078	
Northern Europe	0.096		0,075	
Non-EU countries (Turkey)	0.611		0,320	
Observations	5251		5309	
Prob > chi2	0.000		0.000	
Pseudo R2	0.274		0.135	
Log likelihood	-4550.64		-6257.78	

Level of statistical significance: ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1.

Note: Ethnic background and Openness – Ethnic diversity have not been included as a variable in the case of Turkish data.

Source Authors' calculations

Table 23. Ordered logit model results for country specific samples (Belgium, Netherlands and Spain)

IVs	Belgium		Netherlands		Spain	
	Perception	Willingness to join	Perception	Willingness to join	Perception	Willingness to join
Positive perception about CE	0.775 ***	0.099	0.817 ***	-0.018	0.904 ***	0.086
Familiarity with terms	0.068 **	0.101 ***	0.024	0.034	0.069 ***	0.080 ***
Previous experience	-0.027	-0.704 *	0.666 **	0.475	0.136	0.433 **
Like to repair or make things	0.340	0.642 **	0.088	1.338 ***	-0.118	0.325
Negative impacts	-0.098 *	-0.095 *	-0.106 ***	-0.045	-0.077 ***	-0.030
Drivers	0.718 **	0.604 **	0.938 ***	1.004 ***	0.617 ***	0.590 ***
Barriers to participate_F1	-0.091	-0.083	-0.023	-0.323 **	-0.020	-0.041
Barriers to participate_F2	0.368 **	-0.082	-0.152	0.118	0.138	0.172 *
Barriers to participate_F3	-0.076	0.097	-0.072	-0.039	-0.017	-0.047
Barriers to join_F1	-0.283	0.211	0.109	0.240 **	0.079	0.011
Barriers to join_F2	0.178	-0.041	0.114	0.260 **	-0.078	-0.121
Concerns about ethnic background	-0.097	0.099	-0.151	0.048	-0.212 **	0.172 **
Certificate	0.015	0.107	-0.017	0.310 ***	-0.007	0.175 ***
Openness	0.524	0.098	0.671 **	0.487 *	0.386 *	0.584 ***
Openness – ethnic diversity	0.182	0.241	-0.171	-0.067	-0.055	0.112
Altruistic & biospheric values	0.027	0.021	0.397 *	0.234	0.365 **	0.353 **
Egoistic values	-0.249	-0.207	-0.133	-0.244 **	0.027	0.022
NEP_F1	-0.140	0.261	-0.303	0.018	0.088	0.135
NEP_F2	-0.589 ***	-0.107	-0.055	0.072	-0.048	-0.068
NEP_F3	-0.203	-0.258	0.087	-0.137	0.005	0.021

IVs	Belgium		Netherlands		Spain	
	Perception	Willingness to join	Perception	Willingness to join	Perception	Willingness to join
NEP_F4	0.109	0.216	0.078	-0.049	0.025	-0.084
NEP_F5	0.403	0.271	0.349 **	0.133	-0.015	-0.062
Gender	0.193	-0.602 **	0.271	-0.223	0.298 *	0.025
Education	-0.035	0.123 **	-0.039	-0.029	-0.037	-0.088 ***
Age	0.071	0.140	-0.084	0.068	-0.017	0.173 ***
Urban areas	-0.577	-0.337	-0.007	-0.307	0.086	0.092
Rural areas	0.201	-0.161	0.079	0.356	-0.309	-0.015
Observations	227	229	451	456	714	720
Prob > chi2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Pseudo R2	0.247	0.140	0.264	0.134	0.235	0.125
Log likelihood	-198.172	-275.356	-379.954	-532.277	-570.049	-826.311

Level of statistical significance: ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1.

Note: Ethnic background and openness – ethnic diversity have not been included as questions in the Turkish version of the questionnaire.

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 24. Ordered logit model results for country specific samples (Greece, Lithuania and Turkey)

IVs	Greece		Lithuania		Turkey	
	Perception	Willingness to join	Perception	Willingness to join	Perception	Willingness to join
Positive perception about CE	1.020 ***	0.157	1.883 ***	-0,011	0,898 ***	-0,069
Familiarity with terms	0.055 **	0.044 **	0.073 *	0.053	0,089 **	0,081 **
Previous experience	0.164	1.058 ***	-0.025	-0,037	0,399	-0,315
Like to repair or make things	0.686 **	1.360 ***	-0.045	0.051	-0,440	0,258
Negative impacts	-0.071 **	-0.002	-0.041	-0,027	-0,088 **	-0,044
Drivers	0.939 ***	0.505 ***	0.547 **	0,633 ***	0,777 ***	0,166
Barriers to participate_F1	-0.071	-0.304 **	0.077	0,158	-0,175	-0,641 ***
Barriers to participate_F2	0.139	-0.043	0.150	0,248	0,218	-0,096
Barriers to participate_F3	-0.153	-0.051	-0.315 **	0,110	-0,036	-0,025
Barriers to join_F1	0.012	0.183 *	-0.348 *	0,111	-0,065	0,330 **
Barriers to join_F2	-0.024	-0.085	0.156	0,071	0,012	0,131
Concerns about ethnic background	-0.137	0.109	-0.170	0,022		
Certificate	-0.125	0.021	0.090	0,622 ***	0,128	0,520 ***
Openness	0.351	0.357	0.115	-0,250	0,380	0,807 ***
Openness – ethnic diversity	0.059	-0.032	0.309	0,185		
Altruistic & biospheric values	0.039	0.486 **	0.344	1,055 ***	-0,091	0,652 ***
Egoistic values	-0.116	-0.101	-0.055	0,204	-0,074	0,207
NEP_F1	0.027	0.129	-0.283	-0,430	-0,190	-0,135
NEP_F2	0.073	-0.005	-0.063	0,011	0,002	0,377 **
NEP_F3	0.071	0.039	-0.086	-0,138	0,229	-0,091

IVs	Greece		Lithuania		Turkey	
	Perception	Willingness to join	Perception	Willingness to join	Perception	Willingness to join
NEP_F4	0.052	0.090	-0.282	-0.133	0.262 *	0.153
NEP_F5	0.217	-0.195	0.592 **	-0.005	0.185	0.449 **
Gender	0.414 *	0.047	-0.674 **	-0.487 *	0.218	0.051
Education	-0.017	0.020	-0.013	-0.022	0.050	-0.037
Age	-0.190 **	-0.210 ***	-0.210 *	-0.063	-0.114	0.166 **
Urban areas	0.064	-0.284	0.212	0.458	-0.417	0.020
Rural areas	0.159	0.345	0.585	-0.226	-2.236	2.565 *
Observations	456	459	253	261	366	370
Prob > chi2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Pseudo R2	0.258	0.125	0.408	0.219	0.282	0.288
Log likelihood	-357.166	-521.225	-173.646	-281.533	-274.563	-323.494

Level of statistical significance: ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1.

Note: Ethnic background and openness – ethnic diversity have not been included as a variable in the case of Turkish data.

Source: Authors' calculations

6. KPIs addressed by Task 2.2

The project KPIs which are relevant to this deliverable are the following:

- KPI-9. Urban metabolism and productive systems analysed and optimised based on the project outcomes: 7;
- KPI-10. Socio-economic contexts analysed and optimised based on project outcomes: 7;
- KPI-12. Legislative, governance and taxation contexts analysed and optimised based on the project outcomes: 7.

These KPIs are relevant to the whole second work package. More specifically, Task 2.2 contributes to KPI-9 in the following way. The survey targets general public in each country of the 7 pilot-cities offering insights about people's perceptions, including motivations and barriers regarding the maker movement and maker spaces. The analysis of the survey results enables the identification of patterns which define the maker movement within and beyond each country of the included pilot-cities and point to recommendations on how to optimise maker movement ecosystems in each pilot city.

Regarding KPI-10, the analysis provides demographic information such as occupational status that link indirectly to socio-economic indicators. These findings help to explore the socio-economic status of makers and the general public interested in the movement. Second, the patterns and recommendations identified allow the characterisation and optimisation of the maker movement ecosystem in the countries of the pilot cities.

Finally, in relation to KPI-12, this is of course tackled directly by other tasks. However, this deliverable offers a significant background and evidence to present to policy makers to optimise legislative, governance and taxation contexts. Results presented here -such as results for Q15- provide direct information to local pilot municipalities for assessing potential policy actions for the promotion of collaborative production projects throughout Europe.

7. Summary of key findings

This section provides an overview of the key findings that the survey results have revealed. These findings around public perceptions and willingness to join the maker movement can help us understand the main drivers and barriers in this area, and what needs to be communicated to build awareness and increase people's interest in the maker movement. Further investigation of the public acceptance and awareness will be performed with the local targeted workshops that will be implemented throughout the project lifetime. Combining the results of all these activities can lead local authorities to develop more informed policy recommendations and updated strategic plans and interventions, helping to achieve a wider uptake of the maker movement across Europe.

Results have shown that positive perceptions about CE, familiarity with terms related to the maker movement and previous experience constitute significant parameters positively affecting both overall perceptions and willingness to join the maker movement. Moreover, self-definition as a person who likes to repair or make things is another aspect that positively affects our dependent variables. The degree to which individuals agree with the possible **drivers** to join the maker movement was positively associated with both perceptions and the willingness to join (irrespective of the specific reason). At the same time, reasons perceived as **barriers** - both for participating and joining makerspaces - were significant only in some cases, without indicating any specific patterns. Another interesting finding is that the **provision of a certificate** might also act as a driver for joining makerspaces in most cases (total sample, Netherlands, Spain, Lithuania and Turkey).

In terms of **individual characteristics**, the results indicate that openness and altruistic and biospheric values are individual characteristics that positively affect both overall perceptions and willingness to join. On the other hand, egoistic values have not been found statistically significant in any case. In terms of environmental beliefs, only some of the factors deriving from the NEP scale indicate significance without any specific pattern between the samples. In addition, when it comes to **demographic characteristics**, we have seen that gender and age are the only ones affecting perceptions and willingness to join in most cases, with education being significant in only two country cases (Belgium and Spain). It is interesting to notice that being a woman positively affects the overall perception for makerspaces, but it has a negative impact on willingness to join makerspaces. We find a different pattern in the case of Lithuania where women are also less positive towards makerspaces. In the case of age, we can see that older persons tend to have more positive perceptions regarding makerspaces, whereas younger persons are more willing to join them. Finally, **spatial characteristics** referring to the type of the area where the participants reside have not been found significant in any of the cases.

The analysis offered us also the opportunity to investigate some interesting characteristics regarding each pilot case separately. In this regard, we have identified the **main attitudes towards welcoming, visiting and using the facilities of makerspaces** in the 7 pilot cities. Overall, we have seen that there is an overall positive attitude towards these aspects of potential citizen engagement in all cases. Moreover, it was possible to provide additional information regarding the **main maker activities** that participants wanted to do in each city. In general, we can say that some variations have been found between the pilot cities, as in some of them survey participants wanted to focus on more artistic activities, whereas in some others their main focus was on more traditional production areas. At the same time, **reasons for joining a makerspace** were diversified between our case studies offering meaningful insights to policy makers. In any case, these insights reflect only a very small sample in most cases, and thus, we should consider them only as preliminary indications.

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appendix 1 Survey questionnaire

Welcome note

Dear participant, welcome to our survey!

The survey lasts approximately 15 minutes. There are no right or wrong answers, this is all about your views. All data are anonymised, and your privacy is guaranteed. Thank you for helping us gather relevant information!

What is the Pop-Machina project?

Pop-Machina aims to demonstrate the potential of the maker movement and collaborative production for the EU circular economy. The project brings people together to form circular maker communities in 7 European cities and supports them with tools, training programmes and dedicated business services to overcome scaling issues, while also contributing to improving sustainable urban development and benefiting the local community and society through circular solutions. With this survey, we aim to collect information regarding peoples' perceptions and opinions on the maker movement and existing initiatives in their area.

Informed consent

This privacy policy details information collection practices related to your personal data and other related information and the limited manner in which the Pop-Machina project will use and disclose the information provided to us when you responded the survey.

By participating in the survey, you voluntarily consent to the collection and use of your information by Pop-Machina as set forth in this privacy policy. If you have any questions concerning this privacy policy or our data collection practices you may contact us at info@white-research.eu. We reserve the right to change this privacy policy at any time and inform all participants about the updates.

In addition to your opinion, we are collecting some personal information such as age, country of residence and educational status for socio-demographic purposes. The collected data will be saved and used until the end of the research period of the Pop-Machina project. The data will be only used for the purpose of the Pop-Machina project, funded under the European Union Horizon 2020 programme, aiming to promote makerspaces and the maker movement across Europe.

The lawfulness of the processing of personal data is determined pursuant to Article 6 of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). With respect to personal data, the processing of personal data is based on consent.

Introduction to the topic

Q1 - To what extent are you familiar with the following items?

(1 = Not at all familiar; 2 = Slightly Familiar; 3 = Somewhat familiar; 4 = Moderately familiar; 5 = Extremely Familiar)

	1	2	3	4	5
Q1_1 - Maker movement					
Q1_2 - Makerspace					
Q1_3 - Circular economy					
Q1_4 - Collaborative production					
Q1_5 - Sustainable urban development & regeneration					

Q2 - Do you have previous experience with the maker movement?

Maker movement represents a number of people committed to creatively design and build goods and materials.

- Yes
- No

Q3_1 - Please specify the type of experience:

Please select one option.

- I have heard of the maker movement
- I have an acquaintance/friend who is a maker
- I have participated in a maker activity
- I have used a makerspace to develop a project
- Other

Q3_2 - Could you please specify the type of experience?

Q4 - Do you consider yourself as a person who likes to make or repair things?

- Yes
- No

Q5_1 - In what type of activities would you be interested in a maker community (e.g. a local workshop)? You can select multiple options.

- Repair consumer goods
- 3D printing
- Digital fabrication tools
- Hardware, machining, etc.
- Art, painting, etc.
- Audio and visual production
- Software programming, etc.
- Photography, cinematography, photo editing, etc.
- Woodworking, etc.
- Metalworking, smithing, etc.
- Papercraft, origami, etc.
- Handcraft (e.g. bags, jewellery, knitting, sewing)
- Sculpting, ceramics, etc.
- None of the above
- Other

Q5_2 - Could you please specify the type of activities which you would be interested doing in a maker community?

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Perceptions

To ensure that all participants have a common understanding of the terminology used in the survey, the definitions of maker movement, makerspaces, circular economy and collaborative production are provided below. We invite you to read these definitions before answering the survey's questions.

Maker movement represents a number of people committed to creatively design and build goods and materials. For example, the construction of a table by designing and producing its components in 3D prototyping machine in an open makerspace.

Makerspace is a place in which people with shared interests, especially in computing or technology, can gather to work on projects while sharing ideas, equipment and knowledge.

Circular economy is an industrial economy that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design.

Collaborative production refers to the collaboration of groups of individuals to design, produce to distribute goods, and is related to the idea that it is the community that decides what to produce.

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?
 (1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; DK/NO = Don't know/No opinion)

Q6 - My overall perception about:

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q6_1 - makerspaces is positive. Makerspace is a place in which people with shared interests, especially in computing or technology, can gather to work on projects while sharing ideas, equipment and knowledge.						
Q6_2 - circular economy is positive. Circular economy is an industrial economy that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design.						
Q6_3 - the transition towards circular economy is negative.						

Q7 - My participation in makerspaces:

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q7_1 - will not provide any benefits to me.						
Q7_2 - will improve my skills.						
Q7_3 - will have a positive impact on my region.						
Q7_4 - is something that I consider as a hobby.						
Q7_5 - aims to open professional opportunities.						

Q8 - I would

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q8_1 - welcome/invite a makerspace in my area.						
Q8_2 - visit a makerspace in my area.						
Q8_3 - use the facilities of a makerspace in my area.						

Q9 - I would like makerspaces to:

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q9_1 - enhance skills and improve the employability of local community members.						
Q9_2 - act as open places for discussion about our community concerns.						
Q9_3 - generate solutions for the local challenges of my community.						
Q9_4 - empower local citizens to become more sensitive about environmental sustainability.						
Q9_5 - involve vulnerable groups (e.g. migrants, elderly, people with disabilities, etc.).						
Q9_6 - contribute to lowering the environmental footprint of my city/country.						
Q9_7 - remain in a small-scale operation and contribute towards their local community's economy.						
Q9_8 - scale-up their production and contribute towards a more circular economy across Europe.						

Q10 - I would like my local municipality to:

You can select multiple options.

- bring together the makers of my city to develop solutions to its challenges
- finance the development of makerspaces in my city
- provide free access to makerspaces
- provide non-financial incentives to the members of the maker community to participate (e.g. business support services)
- increase awareness about the contribution of the maker movement to sustainable urban development and regeneration
- none of the above
- don't know/no opinion

Barriers

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

(1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; DK/NO = Don't know/No opinion)

Q11 - Regarding my participation in a makerspace, I am concerned about the following aspects:

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q11_1 - I lack information about makerspaces and their actions.						
Q11_2 - I lack financial incentives to support it and its development.						
Q11_3 - I lack the necessary technical skills and there is no tutoring available that can assist me.						
Q11_4 - I feel that there is no physical space available in my region that would fit the needs of such maker community.						
Q11_5 - I feel makerspaces lack proper health and safety regulations and clarity about responsibility in case of an accident.						
Q11_6 - I am worried that there is low participation rate.						

Q11_7 - I am worried I do not have the necessary time to join.						
Q11_8 - I am worried I do not know how to start.						
Q11_9 - I am worried I do not know where to go.						

Q12 - I believe that makerspaces:

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q12_1 - have negative health impacts on my region.						
Q12_2- have negative environmental impacts on my region						
Q12_3 - produce waste.						
Q12_4 - cause noise.						

Q13 - I would like to join a makerspace but:

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q13_1 - I do not know if there is a makerspace in my region.						
Q13_2 - I have concerns about my age.						
Q13_3- I feel that my gender is not equally represented.						
Q13_4 - I feel that I do not fit in due to my ethnic background.						
Q13_5 - There are no makerspaces in my region.						
Q13_6 - I am not sure if I have the right skills.						

Q14_1 - According to your opinion, is there any other barrier that hinders your participation in a makerspace?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know/No opinion

Q14_2 - Could you please specify?

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Drivers

Q15_1 - I would consider joining a makerspace to:

You can select multiple options.

- Access tools or mentorship
- Learn new technical skills
- Develop ideas
- Provide a valuable service to the community
- Share my knowledge and skills with others
- Improve my employability skills
- Make new business contacts
- Promote sustainable development in my community
- Learn how I could use my skills to setup a small business
- Meet individuals with common interests
- None of the above
- Other

Q15_2 - Could you please specify?

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To what extent do you agree with the following statement?

(1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; DK/NO = Don't know/No opinion)

Q16 - I would be more willing to join a makerspace if I could get a certificate of attendance.	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
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Willingness to join, openness and values

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

(1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; DK/NO = Don't know/No opinion)

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q17_1 - I am willing to join the maker movement.						
Q17_2 - I believe makerspaces would be useful to my community.						
Q17_3 - My close family (parents, children, siblings, partner) would support my decision to join the maker movement.						
Q17_4 - I believe that the makerspaces are here to stay.						

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q18_1 - I do not like trying new things and would rather stick with what I know.						
Q18_2 - I try to learn something new every day.						
Q18_3 - I understand that people can have different attitudes toward certain things than I do.						
Q18_4 - I am open towards listening what others have to say.						
Q18_5 - I learn a great deal from people with differing beliefs.						
Q18_6 - I enjoy having (racial) diversity in my community.						
Q18_7 - I feel that an opportunity to learn about the cultures of others is something to be treasured.						

How important are the following aspects to you?

(1=Not at all important; 2=Slightly important; 3=Neutral; 4=Moderately important; 5=Very important; DK/NO = Don't Know/No opinion)

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q19_1 - Equality: equal opportunity for all.						
Q19_2 - Social justice: correcting injustice, care for the weak.						
Q19_3 - Being helpful: working for the welfare of others.						
Q19_4 - Respecting the earth: harmony with other species.						
Q19_5 - Unity with nature: fitting into nature.						
Q19_6- Protecting the environment: preserving nature.						
Q19_7 - Wealth: material possessions, money.						
Q19_8 - Authority: the right to lead or command.						
Q19_9 - Influence: having an impact on people and events.						

Environmental attitude

Listed below are statements about the relationship between humans and the environment.

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

(1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; DK/NO = Don't know/No opinion)

	1	2	3	4	5	DK/NO
Q20_1 - We are approaching the limit of the number of people the Earth can support.						
Q20_2 - Humans have the right to modify the natural environment to suit their needs.						
Q20_3 - When humans interfere with nature it often produces disastrous consequences.						
Q20_4 - Human ingenuity will ensure that we do not make the Earth unlivable.						
Q20_5 - Humans are seriously abusing the environment.						
Q20_6 - The Earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them.						
Q20_7 - Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist.						
Q20_8 - The balance of nature is strong enough to cope with the impacts of modern industrial nations.						
Q20_9 - Despite our special abilities, humans are still subject to the laws of nature.						
Q20_10 - The so-called 'ecological crisis' facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated.						
Q20_11 - The Earth is like a spaceship with very limited room and resources.						
Q20_12 - Humans were meant to rule over the rest of nature.						
Q20_13 - The balance of nature is very delicate and easily upset.						
Q20_14 - Humans will eventually learn enough about how nature works to be able to control it.						
Q20_15 - If things continue on their present course, we will soon experience a major ecological catastrophe.						

General information

Q21 - Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

Q22 - Age

- 18-24 years
- 25-29 years
- 30-39 years
- 40-49 years
- 50-59 years
- 60+ years

Q23 - Please select your country:

Q24 - Place of residence

- City centre
- Suburbs
- Town
- Rural area

Q25 - Education

- No education
- Primary education
- Secondary education (lower)
- Secondary education (upper)
- Higher education (Bachelor's degree or equivalent)
- Higher education (MSc, PhD or equivalent)

Q26 - Activity status

Please select one option.

- Employed (full-time)
- Employed (part-time)
- Unemployed
- Student
- Household activity
- Retired
- Other

Q27_1 - Do you define yourself as any of the following?

You can select multiple options.

- Maker
- Artist
- Engineer

- Inventor
- Designer
- Entrepreneur
- None of the above
- Other

Q27_2 - Could you please specify?

If you would not like to mention how you would define yourself, you can leave this field blank.

Survey end

Thank you for taking part into this survey and contributing to our understanding of what people think about makerspaces!

Your input will help us a great deal to identify key elements and perceptions that should be considered during the implementation of our project. Do you have any questions or comments? You can contact us at info@white-research.eu.

Want to keep in touch with Pop-Machina and learn about the activities that are taking place in the project's pilot-cities?

Check our website, subscribe to our newsletter and follow us on social media!

Pop-Machina

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Youtube: [Pop Machina Project](#)

About Pop-Machina

Pop-Machina aims to demonstrate the power and potential of the maker movement and collaborative production for the EU circular economy. We draw from a number of cut-edge technologies (factory-of-the-future, blockchain) and disciplines (urban planning, architecture) to provide the support necessary to overcome scaling issues; a typical drawback of collaborative production; to find the areas more in need of our intervention and to reconfigure unused spaces. We put forth an elaborate community engagement program to network, incentivize and stimulate through maker faires and events existing and new maker communities in all our municipalities. We build upon the current informal curriculum for maker skills development by nurturing the social side and we put educators and makers together to exchange ideas on the training modalities. A particular focus on the skill development of women and vulnerable groups will aim to empower these (underrepresented) segments to partake actively in collaborative production. In every pilot area we will demonstrate business oriented collaborative production of feasible and sustainable concepts from secondary raw material or other sustainable inputs, based on the needs and preferences of the local stakeholders. A thorough impact assessment framework with increased scope (e.g. social) will be codesigned with stakeholders after short basic assessment trainings and will be used in the assessment of our pilot work. Based on the findings we will kick-start a series of policy events to discuss openly – without pushing our results – the tax and legal barriers that hamper collaborative production.

Coordinator

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Partners

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